

MICHELE SANVICO

THE APENNINE SIBYL

A MYSTERY AND A LEGEND

SIBILLINI MOUNTAIN RANGE, THE CHTHONIAN LEGEND¹

PART 2

5. Earthquakes: in search of an otherwordly contact

In the preceding paragraphs we have provided an illustration of the close relationship which exists between the Sibillini Mountain Range and its marked seismic character.

Across the last centuries and millennia, most devastating earthquakes have been occurring in the area on a recurrent basis. The very face of the mountain range is affected by the largest events. Smaller earthquakes ceaselessly hit the territory, many of them just above the threshold of human sensitivity. Vibrations and rumbles may be often heard. Everybody

¹ Released on March 25th 2020 on <https://www.researchgate.net/> and <https://www.academia.edu/>

knows that a catastrophic earthquake might happen anytime, announced by sequences of smaller tremors, or even totally unheralded. They all know that sudden death may ensue, and that within the space of a few seconds their own life and the life of their family members may be subject to a dramatic change or even be terminated altogether under the debris of a collapsing roof.

This is what actually happened on August, 24th and October, 30th 2016.

However, we have been discussing the life in the region and the perception of the seismic waves as they are today, in reference to contemporary men and women who live in the twenty-first century, fully surrounded by a framework of culture and science, with comprehensive information being given to them about the true nature of earthquakes as an effect of the mutual displacement of the titanic plates that make up the Earth's crust.

But what about people's credences, beliefs and fears in ages in which Alfred Wegener's theory on continental drift was still to come? What was life in the Sibillini Mountain Range when nobody knew about plate tectonics, fault lines and seismogenic layers?

Fig. 65 - Alfred Wegener's *Entstehung der Kontinente und Ozeane* (*The Origin of Continents and Oceans*) published in Braunschweig in 1920, with a diagram showing the drift of continents (p. 61)

What did it mean to live amid the Sibillini Mountain Range in the Middle Ages, or in classical antiquity, or even before the coming of Roman legions?

Earthquakes were there already. Their typical manifestations were the same as in our present days and across the most recent centuries.

How did people react to earthquakes?

We will now examine in more detail the characters and way of life of the populations which inhabited the central Apennines before the Roman conquest. Because they, too, were subject to the devastating effects of earthquakes on their lives, dwellings, and families.

They were frightened, too. And possibly their fear was far more overwhelming than it is in our contemporary age.

5.1 Living amid the mountains in antiquity

In 290 B.C., Roman consul Manius Curius Dentatus entered with his troops the mountainous region of central Apennines and overcame the Sabines, the ancient population which inhabited the region which is known today as the Sibillini Mountain Range:

«After the Latins they [the Romans] attacked the race of the Sabines, who, forgetful of the relationship formed under Titus Tatius, had become as it were infected by the spirit of the Latins and had joined in their wars. During the consulship of Curius Dentatus, the Romans laid waste with fire and sword all the tract of country which is enclosed by the Nera, the Anio and the sources of the Velinus, and bounded by the Adriatic Sea. By this conquest so large a population and so vast a territory was reduced, that even he who had won the victory could not tell which was of the greater importance».

[In the original Latin text: «A Latinis adgressus est gentem Sabinorum, qui immemores factae sub Tito Tatiao adfinitatis quodam contagio belli se Latinis adiunxerant. Sed Curio Dentato consule omnem eum tractum, qua

Nar, Anio, fontesque Velini, Hadriano tenus mari igni ferroque vastavit. Qua victoria tantum hominum, tantum agrorum redactum in potestatem, ut in utro plus esset nec ipse posset aestimare qui vicerat»].

In this excerpt taken from Lucius Annaeus Florus' *Epitomae de Tito Livio*, we see the Romans advance into the territory lying by the Via Salaria, the road which crosses the central Apennines, storming deep into the area set within the course of river Nera and the ancient town of Nursia. From then on, that land will be part of a new 'praefectura' under Roman control.

Fig. 66 - The passage on the Roman conquest of Sabine from Lucius Annaeus Florus' *Epitomae de Tito Livio* (manuscript Pal. Lat. 894 preserved at the Universitätsbibliothek in Heidelberg), folium 9r

In antiquity, the Sibillini Mountain Range was known with the name of 'Tetrica rupes', which means 'gloomy, frightful mountain', as mentioned by Vergilius in Book VII of his poem *Aeneid*, in describing the Italian troops that were being sent against Aeneas (vv. 706-713):

«Here comes the great Army of the ancient lineage of the Sabines [...] after Sabines were given a part of Rome [...] and those who live at the dreadful Tetricus cliff».

[In the original Latin text: «Ecce Sabinorum prisco de sanguine magnum Agmen [...] postquam in partem data Roma Sabinis [...] qui Tetricae horrentis rupes»].

Fig. 67 - The excerpt from Vergilius' *Aeneid* containing the sentence on the 'Tetricae horrentis rupes' (manuscript Harley 2772, British Library, folium 5r)

As detailed in our previous paper *World of the Sibyl: the Italian Apennines and the Sibillini Mountain Range*, this name is further confirmed by fifth-century scholar Servius Marius Honoratus («the Tetricus mountain is a barren, towering mountain, where stern men are said 'tetricos', sullen and gloomy»), first-century consul Silius Italicus («with him come the soldiers of [...] Reate sacred to the great Mother of the Gods, and Nursia the abode of snow, and warriors from the Tetricus cliff»), and Marcus Terentius Varro («even now there are several species of wild cattle in various places. [...] For there are many wild goats in Italy in the vicinity of Mount Fiscellum and Mount Tetrica»).

But the relation between Romans and Sabines dates back to much earlier times, with the legendary tale of 'The Abduction of the Sabine Women' which is part of the myth on the foundation of Rome itself.

On the other side of the 'Tetricus Mons' lived another ancient population, the Picenes. According to an ancient tradition, they were of Sabine origin, having moved to the eastern side of their native territory in search of new land, as reported by many classical authors, including first-century geographer Strabo:

«The Picenes came here from Sabine, led by a woodpecker that showed the way to their forefathers. From this their name is derived: they call this bird

'Picus', and they consider it sacred to Ares. They are settled from the mountains down to the plains and the sea».

Fig. 68 - The Picenes as mentioned in Strabo's *Rerum Geographarum*, in a printed Greek-Latin version published in Basel in 1771 (p. 263)

The Picenes came under the influence of Rome in the same years as the Sabines, following the third Samnite War (298 - 290 B.C.), in which they fought as allied of the Romans.

It is out of the scope of the present work to illustrate the results and assumptions of modern research as to the origin of both the Sabines and the Picenes, the two populations of interest for our enquiry into the origin of the legends of the Sibillini Mountain Range. It is sufficient to report here that the archeological investigation has ascertained the presence of man-made artifacts in the area since the age of Neolithic, set between 5,000 and 3,000 B.C. In the Iron Age, roughly starting after 1,000 B.C., the Sabines may have possibly moved eastwards, beyond the Sibillini Mountain Range and towards the sea, giving rise to an offspring of Picene settlers in the southern portion of today's Marche.

What sort of men inhabited that remote, isolated territory, before the Romans came? How did they live? And where?

On the western side of the 'Tetrica rupes', the Sabines lived in a territory that was only sparsely inhabited, and strongly marked by the custom of transhumance, which implied the seasonal transfer of livestock from the grazing grounds of southern Italy to the grassy expands set beneath Mount Vettore, in Norcia and on today's Pian Grande: «transhumance and trade were the primary forms of human activities; an almost uninterrupted woodland, including wooded valleys, left some space to vast clearings used for livestock grazing and only limited, essential farming carried out by rivers and streams [...] within the framework of a network of pathways which crossed the Apennines for horizontal and vertical transhumance, the key to a deep, archetypical interpretation of the economic history of this land» (Paolo Camerieri, *La centuriazione dell'ager Nursinus*, in *Nursia e l'ager Nursinus - Un distretto sabino dalla praefectura al municipium*, edited by Simone Sisani, 2013).

The character of the whole place, set by the tallest mountains of the Sibillini Mountain Range, suggests that «livestock management and trade were the main source for production of wealth, especially at the Plains of Castelluccio (Pian Grande, Pian Piccolo, Pian Perduto), marked by cattle breeding on both a local and transhumant basis» (Romano Cordella et al., *La Sabina settentrionale: Norcia, Cascia e Valnerina romane*, 2007).

So it is not a surprise to note that, in this area, no significant urban settlement has ever been established, apart from the town of Norcia, on the westernmost borders of the Sibillini Mountain Range. In antiquity, Norcia itself was no large settlement: according to archeological evidence, simple huts only begin to appear starting from the Iron Age, around ninth century B.C., subsequently replaced, two centuries later, by enclosed walls, accompanied by a burial ground which contains the remains of wealthy male warriors. But the largest portion of the present urban area will be extensively built only after the Roman conquest (Liliana Costamagna, *Dinamiche insediative tra Umbria e Sabina in età preromana*, in *Nursia e l'ager Nursinus - Un distretto sabino dalla praefectura al municipium*, edited by Simone Sisani, 2013).

Even the ancient worship site set at the foot of the mounts which lie just outside Norcia, Forca di Ancarano, seems to have been in operations between the seventh and the fifth century B.C., with a void in the subsequent century until the arrival of the Romans (Simone Sisani, *Da Curio Dentato a Vespasio Pollione: conquista e romanizzazione del distretto nursino*, in *Nursia e l'ager Nursinus - Un distretto sabino dalla praefectura al municipium*, a cura di Simone Sisani, 2013).

Beside Norcia, only scarce traces of settlements can be found in the neighbouring territory. In the adjoining Piana di Santa Scolastica, no remnants of 'villae rusticae' (countryside villas and farms) have been retrieved. Thus it seems reasonable to suppose that «there was alternative settlement scheme based on the presence of a pagus/vicus system [a small administrative district in the countryside including various hamlets, editor's note], a system that has survived up to our present days, as the modern localisation of all tiny villages, set by the antique Roman grid of fields and at constant distance from one another, seems to suggest» (Camerieri, op. cit.). In fact, «we must also note that on the heights which surround the valley of Norcia various significant settlements can be found, that are not to be overlooked if we want to fully understand the settlement process in the area [... at] Monte della Civita, [...] Croce di Norcia, [...] Legogne [... and] Oricchio». The final impression is that «the many inhabited outposts that marked the points of passage into the valley of Norcia were established not as specific settlements, but as parts of the whole valley, in which the various places, though located at distinct points, made up a single community» (Costamagna, op. cit.).

Beyond that, only «small fortified posts in the highlands were present to oversee the trail of transhumance» (Camerieri, op. cit.).

This distribution of settlements hints to «a most scattered ownership of the land [...] which was certainly supported by the presence of buildings dedicated to the dwelling of families, and the processing and storage of agricultural products and cattle [...] with] autonomous farming units, in a dual agricultural/livestock breeding system which was mainly intended for mere subsistence» (Cordella et al., op. cit.).

On the eastern side of the 'Tetrica rupes', the Picenes experimented a different development path, especially from the seventh century B.C. and

mainly in the northern portion of the present province of Marche: «the region was increasingly opening up to outside contacts: Picene communities were acquiring larger quantities of imported goods as well as the technological know-how for manufacturing sophisticated objects locally, [...] from metal to amber, ivory and bone. As a consequence, these communities became richer and [...] gained the ability to accumulate a hitherto unseen wealth» (Corinna Riva, *The Archaeology of Picenum - The Last Decade*, in *Ancient Italy. Regions without Boundaries*, edited by Guy Jolyon Bradley et al., 2007). In this northern area, groups of Senone Gauls settled at the beginning of the fourth century B.C.

In the southern portion of Marche, by the eastern versants of the Sibillini Mountain Range, where the Sabines had moved, this historical, commercial and artistic development process was certainly less extended, owing to the impervious nature of the mountainous area set in the inland; yet, «from the ninth century B.C. some major central settlements, [...] Ripatransone, Castignano and Rotella, developed on high ground a good ten kilometres distant from one another and each surrounded by a cemetery». These settlements were located just on the eastern slopes of the Sibillini Mountain Range. These «inland centres grew in the subapennine zone, along the river routes and close to the mountain passes where they controlled the flow of goods from the Tyrrhenian region». (Riva, op. cit.).

However, the hamlets of Montefortino, Montegallo and Montemonaco, set by the very slopes of Mount Vettore and Mount Sibyl, seem to be of much later origin, with only the former dating back to the age of Roman Empire, and the other two being established in late antiquity. Insufficient archeological excavations and lack of findings make it impossible to ascertain the nature of the settlements in the area before the Romans came, even though we can suppose that small outposts may have existed for the control of the tracks which led to the high grounds and grasslands of Pian Grande and the land of the Sabines beyond.

This is the overall picture which is provided to us by history and archeology.

Now, let's try to take advantage of the above information, with a view to merging the available data with the scenario we have been sketching in the

preceding paragraphs on the peculiar role that earthquakes have played amid the Sibillini Mountain Range across the millennia.

Earthquakes that have been hitting, repeatedly and savagely, those same antique populations: the Sabines and the Picenes.

5.2 Sabines and Picenes before the potency of earthquakes

Sabines and Picenes. From the Iron Age onwards, and possibly even earlier, they and their ancestors have inhabited a same mountainous relief: the 'Tetrica rupes', as Romans called it, or Sibillini Mountain Range as it is called today.

Why this jagged, secluded, unfriendly mountainous ridge, set between the most inviting hills and plains of Umbria and the welcoming coastline of Marche, has ever been inhabited at all?

Human beings have been living there as they were mainly attracted by the presence of an elevated plateau covered with extended grasslands: the Pian Grande, lying right beneath the western side of the fearsome Mount Vettore. It is a sort of unexpected bounty concealed within this inhospitable, wintry region, a real trove hidden amid the most frightful mountains, fully fit for livestock feeding and transhumance to and from other Italian regions.

And, amid a territory which was marked by elevated mountains and impenetrable woods, there was another area in which men could comfortably settle: it was the the grassy valley of Norcia, today's Plain of St. Scolastica, where water was abundant, extensive space for farming was available, and the high grounds beneath Mount Vettore could be easily access and controlled. There, the first nucleus of the town of Norcia was founded, a small settlement that will undergo significant extension only after the arrival of Rome's rule.

This latter area was equally set on the western side of the Sibillini Mountain Range, as the Pian Grande was, while on the other side of the mountains their eastern versants were not provided with any equivalent

space for the establishment of significant settlements, the wooded hills which rapidly tend to ascend to the steep slopes of the main cliffs.

Thus, a bounty was hidden there. It was not a land of barren mountains, merely. Plains were there. Huge, extended plateaus, especially on the western side of the elevated ridges. Rich, fertile land. Two wide expanses of grasslands which, once deprived of their woods, could feed large numbers of animals, both local cattle and livestock transferred seasonally from distant territories. The people who controlled the generous grazing lands set on the western boundaries of the Sibillini Mountain Range had a remarkable source of subsistence and significant power in their hands.

Fig. 69 - The Sibillini Mountain Range with the bountiful plateaus which are most fit for cattle feeding and farming of selected crops

So, between the Iron Age and the conquests of the Romans, in the centuries which span from 1,000 B.C. to 290 B.C., men inhabited the area: a single main settlement was there, Norcia, though very small with respect to its future urban development under the Romans; a number of hamlets were scattered around this area, and possibly also on the eastern side of the Sibillini Mountain Range, though possibly the latter were not subject to any rule exercised by Norcia; small outposts guarded the trails that led to Pian Grande, perhaps on both the eastern and western sides of Mount Vettore and the high cliffs. In a hard, unfriendly environment, peasants living in

local, scattered communities attended to subsistence farming; they were also shepherds, who used to drive their herds to the grazing grounds in the highlands; trashumance was possibly being carried out in some sort of seminal forms, as it is not known whether this custom was already in place in such early times. Circulation of goods was limited, with no remarkable instance of significant wealth found in burial grounds, apart from single tombs of warriors.

Such were the people who inhabited the Sibillini Mountain Range from the Iron Age onwards: Sabines and Picenes, peasants and shepherds, who in small villages lived a life of hard work in a harsh natural environment, by the slopes of deserted, elevated cliffs of imposing majesty, taking advantage of the large plains which were found in the area.

In this scenario, we must always remember that if the Sibillini Mountain Range conceals a sort of bounty - the extended plateaus of grassy land - for the people who chose to live under their shadow, the same fastnesses, out of their underlying geological structure and the mighty strain exerted by powerful subterranean forces - hid a terrifying curse.

That curse was earthquakes.

Because - as we saw in previous paragraphs - from time to time, a mighty, terrifying earthquake came upon them. Abruptly.

Death and destruction arrived and swept the whole land.

Below their feet, the ground began to shake as if a monster beneath were trying to unchain itself and break into the world of men. Before their very eyes, the mountains screamed and ripped, and portions of them went down. Their wives, their children and they themselves were crushed, and perished under the wrecks of their poor dwellings, being smashed down by the frantic blows struck by the giant fists of a deity.

And it was not only a matter of recurrent devastation, with the annihilation of their houses and families.

They actually lived their whole life under the ceaseless threat of earthquakes. They were immersed in the ghastly vibrations of the seismic

waves, coming unheralded at night. They often happened to hear the roar which surged from the depths of the ground, always fearing whether that blood-curdling noise was about to raise to a fiendish bellow; or, it was going to appease instead to a low murmur, leaving the dreaded destruction for the next time.

Furthermore, after a primary seismic shock, the local population lived long periods of time interspersed with secondary aftershocks, some of them of significant magnitude. And those periods could even last years.

Fig. 70 - A surface crevice on the side of Mount Porche, a peak set between Mount Vettore and Mount Sibyl, caused by the earthquakes occurred in 2016

Sabines and Picenes. They lived amid the Sibillini Mountain Range. And they were terrified.

Across the Iron Age, no rational knowledge, no scientific explanation was available to them. No plate tectonics, no localisation of fault lines, no analysis of seismic data was known to them.

In addition to that, we have also to consider that they had no information at all about the earthquakes which used to occur in other places of the world. They knew nothing of what happened in other seismic areas, in the Italian peninsula or across the Mediterranean Sea. There was no education, no news, no perception of the characteristics and natural unfolding of any other similar events.

They were alone. They were scared. They feared for their own lives. And they possibly thought that the place in which they lived, today's Sibillini Mountain Range, was some sort of very special place.

And so they started to have their own dream. Their own legends.

The mountains moved. The mountains screamed. The mountains were alive. Or, maybe, some thing that was alive lived beneath the mountains.

And their dream possibly was: the earthquake was a monster; the earthquake was an enraged deity; the earthquake was some sort of demonic entity, which was concealed beneath those impressive, precipitous peaks.

In our conjecture, within the model we are currently developing on the origin of the legends which inhabit the Sibillini Mountain Range, this is the assumption we are trying to consider: across the many centuries which are part of the Iron Age, before the arrival of the Roman, local people began to develop some sort of specific dream, a legendary narrative, and a possible cult, with relation to the nature and potential worship of earthquakes, considered a kind of fiendish being.

A fiendish being which they certainly wished to placate. To avoid fear, destruction, and death.

We stress the point that what we are going to propose in the paragraphs that follow is basically a conjecture, which will need to be put under trial through a series of further studies and confirmations, possibly including further on-site excavations; and yet, as we will see later, it is a model that is fully based on reasonable grounds, among which the observation of the actual seismic behaviour of the Sibillini Mountain Range, the legendary tradition on the Sibyl's Cave and Pilate's Lake that we have fully analysed in our previous works, with a particular reference to the papers *Sibillini*

Mountain Range: the legend before the legends and Sibillini Mountain Range, a cave and lake to the Otherworld, and the framework proposed by the historical and archeological research on the local populations which inhabited the area for centuries before the Roman rule.

In our conjectural model, a first issue that the ancient inhabitants of the Sibillini Mountain Range, Sabines and Picenes, had possibly to confront with was how to establish a tentative contact with the mighty powers beneath.

They needed to communicate with them. They needed to talk to them. Because, without the establishment of a communication link, there was no way to ask them to stop the earthquake. An earthquake they were fearing would soon come, or the multiple earthquakes which used to follow a powerful shake.

So, where to address them? Was there any specific site where to go and implore the evil gods beneath to hold their rage and have mercy on them?

Yes, the Sibillini Mountain Range, the land of earthquakes, proposed a most fit site.

Actually, the mountains proposed two of them. Both were utterly frightful, and certainly fully apt to address and worship the divine beings which lived beneath the rock.

They were a Lake and a Cave.

And we know them very well.

5.3 The lake and cave, landmarks to earthquake potencies

As we saw in the previous paragraph, we are conjecturing that the ancient populations of peasants and shepherds which lived amid the Sibillini Mountain Range, the Sabines and Picenes, scattered across small hamlets on both sides of the mountainous ridge, affrighted by the recurrent earthquakes that hit the land, and being ceaselessly reminded of the impending threat by the neverending tremors and rumbles which came

from beneath, had developed their own legendary dream: the earthquake was the sign of some thing that lived under the mountains. For their own safety, they needed to establish a contact with the monster, deity, or demon beneath, so as to ask for its mercy and appease its cyclical rage.

The first issue, for those men, was, of course, how and where to establish such terrifying contact.

A tricky issue, because the dwellings of supernatural, fiendish beings are not easy to find in our ordinary world.

But the Sibillini Mountain Range actually offered a perfect site to the purpose. Indeed, the appropriate sites were two.

We must remember that those men did not live by a peaceful shore by the sea, or on a vast plain run by sleepy, winding rivers.

They lived by appalling mountains, a sort of impregnable fortress standing out from the main Apennine chain, and whose mere sight recalled to the mind ideas of titanic gods and superhuman potencies.

As we described in a previous paper (*A legend for a Roman prefect: the Lakes of Pontius Pilate*), on the southernmost side of this massive ridge raises the titanic shape of Mount Vettore, with its huge, imposing mass, an arched behemoth that overwhelms the whole mountainous region with its elevated top and vertiginous, sinister cliffs.

Deeply enclosed within the precipitous arms of this giant of stone, a small mirror of pure, clear water lay in silence and stillness. A Lake. It waited in its solitary nest, surrounded by looming, overhanging versants of vertical rock.

It was an icy, crystal-like surface, set at the bottom of Mount Vettore's glacial cirque, high up amid sheer walls of rock, quietly reflecting the sky above.

Three millennia ago as today (but in our present days the Lake is split in two owing to the ruinous fall of rocks from the overhanging cliffs and the partial collapse of a portion of its northern shore, as Pio Rajna reports in his

article *Nei paraggi della Sibilla di Norcia*), whoever had the chance to climb the gigantic mountain and visit the place hidden between the cliffs of rock was struck by the feeling of indistinct, dumbfounded awe that seizes a human soul when left alone before this overpowering might, which echoes any step that may be taken, any sound and any word that might be uttered, with hesitant whispers, by the astounded visitor.

Fig. 71 - The Lakes of Pilate as they appear today

The Lake was, and still is, a truly blood-curdling place. A sort of theatrical scenery, ready for some kind of eerie performance. It was a setting where an inexplicable, dreadful event seemed to be about to happen. It was totally desolate, and totally inhabited.

Was that the one and only site where man could have fancied to establish a ghastly contact with the legendary, supernatural powers which they reputed may be concealed beneath the Sibillini Mountain Range?

No, there was a second site.

And it was not far from the Lake. You only needed to look down, from that very Lake, along the valley which followed, and still follows, the displacement route of the antique glacier that once was nested within the rocky arms of Mount Vettore: there, at a distance of 5.2 miles, and in full line of sight, Mount Sibyl raises its crowned peak.

Mount Sibyl, whose the sinister pinnacle could be reached through a long walk which started from the western cliffs of Mount Vettore, heading to Mount Argentella, and up to vertiginous paths running along the crests, which, by cutting through the dizzy peaks of Palazzo Borghese and Mount Porche, led at last - beyond Vallelunga's Peak - to the crowned mountain.

Fig. 72 - The crowned peak of Mount Sibyl

Because beneath the very top of it, there was a ring of solid, barren rock; a sheer wall, rising for a few dozen feet, which encircled the uppermost region of the mount: that was the crown, a crown of overhanging rock. It was like an unassailable wall carved in the mount's body, a sort of token of some sort of kingly dominance. And its ramparts opened the way to the uppermost region of the mount, a realm which seemed to be apparently forbidden to mortal beings, surrounded as it was by sheer ravines and, on the northwestern side, by a precipitous versant, which fell abruptly for thousands of feet down to the grisly and appalling gorge of the Infernaccio, where the river Tenna gurgled, unseen in the distance, among inaccessible cliffs of perpendicular rock.

And, actually, the crown appeared to guard a fateful spot, a place of the greatest significance: on the very top of the mount, a ghastly, baleful Cave opened its gloomy jaws on an unknown maze of secret pits and passages. A barren darkness, an unfriendly, almost tangible obscurity from which a cold breath issued forth: a gaping mouth, which seemed to swallow the bodies of men, as those who had ventured into its hollows and caverns and tunnels, and had never come back. It was a desolate place, and totally uninhabited.

In this place, too, the fanciful dreams of the ancient inhabitants of the Sibillini Mountain Range may have found a suitable place where to make attempts at establishing a contact with the subterranean potencies which, in their legendary narratives, controlled and roused the earthquakes: the Cave as a sort of gateway to address the fiendish being that used to unleash death and destruction over their land.

A Lake and a Cave. Two landmarks, two peculiar geographical features, set within the same territory, the Sibillini Mountain Range, in which earthquakes played a major role in the life of the local people.

Two features that are set within a mountainous range marked by the peculiar presence of a glacial valley, a unique landform in the central Apennines, and an impressive, emotional setting for the staging of legendary tales.

It was at the end of the Pleistocene, during the Würm glaciation, a period extending from 100,000 to 10,000 years ago, that the Ice Age produced the most impressive feature which marks Mount Vettore as we know it today: the glacial cirque, a colossal hemicycle carved in the very matrix of the landform, which gives the mount its fantastic, astounding U-shaped structure, a sort of immense horseshoe. A glacier made all this, eroding and grinding the mount's rock and the subjacent valley by its ceaseless motion under the pull of gravity, for hundreds and hundreds of centuries.

The resulting shape in an enclosed, elongated glen of significant size: a sort of titanic, shady womb or lair made of rock, marked on its northernmost tip by Mount Sibyl, and on the southern edge by the arched cliffs of Mount Vettore.

Fig. 73 - The arched shape of Mount Vettore with its enclosed glacial valley running northwards

And, from the Iron Age until the arrival of the Romans, we can suppose that those two features, the Lake and Cave, placed within this giant sheltering den, may have assumed a very specific role.

As points of contact to an appalling, subterranean Otherworld.

5.4 Otherworldly highland shrines

A land recurrently smashed by devastating earthquakes. A territory which lived under the impending threat of ground shaking. The earth itself seemed to be enraged. The very mountains trembled and sometimes even yelled with all their fury. Even in periods when their rage seemed to be appeased, the ground beneath rumbled and warned the men above that some thing was always there, and the time for destruction was only being postponed.

And men's hearts were filled with dread, awe and an urgent alarm.

They needed some kind of action. The leaders of the local communities, scattered on the eastern and western sides of the Sibillini Mountain Range, with a most significant settlement in the area of Norcia, were being put under pressure by the demanding requests of men, women and families which lived in the area, in fear and, from time to time, in sheer terror.

Fig. 74 - The terrifying fault lines activated by the earthquake sequence in 2016 on the western versant of Mount Vettore

For many times, across the Iron Age, the ancient population of peasants and shepherds that lived under the shadows of the mountains had undergone the harrowing trial of a large earthquake. They had experienced the havoc, the loss of lives, the subsequent excruciating sequence of secondary shocks, which had accompanied their grief even for years. In addition to that, throughout their own lives, even in the absence of large earthquakes, they had the chance to sense the vibrations, the roars, the sudden shakings at

night, the hair-raising series of small, ominous tremors that used to come from beneath, all year round.

Throughout the centuries, a legendary narrative on the cause which unleashed the powers of the mountains had certainly been developed. People was asking for it. They wanted to be protected, They wanted to be reassured. They wanted the earthquakes to stop. They wanted the blow not to be struck.

In our conjecture, we imagine that, in the absence of any scientific knowledge, the answer of the leaders, or the most visionary among them, was that the superhuman, otherworldly monster beneath had to be appeased. Men needed to speak to it, somewhere, somehow, and assuage his fury.

Fig. 75 - Fractured ground at the foot of Mount Argentella, 1.5 miles north of Castelluccio di Norcia, as a fearful effect of the earthquakes occurred in 2016

And the only places in the Sibillini Mountain Range in which to establish such a dreadful contact were up there, in the high peaks: at the grim Lake set within the glacial cirque of Mount Vettore; or, at the dark, blood-curdling Cave lying on the crowned mountain, Mount Sibyl.

There lived the fiendish beast. There men should have made their efforts to allay its destructive rage.

We have to consider that we are trying to form a conjecture on a process that lasted many centuries. Here we are not describing a sort of sequence from a movie, in which the ancient villagers gather in fear around their chief priest, as he points up with his raised arm and finger to the fateful cliffs. The elaboration of an oral narrative concerning earthquakes, the reason for their occurrence and the way to avoid destruction certainly was carried out across many hundreds of years, across many generations of men, and with a number of different tales and legendary versions, involving the Lake, the Cave, or both, that today are totally lost to us.

However, in this fragmented framework, we can conjecture that, starting from a remote antiquity, both sites, the Lake and the Cave (today's Lake of Pilate and Sibyl's Cave) began to be considered as highland shrines, sacred to an evil, otherworldly entity connected to earthquake generation.

Highland shrines, small sites dedicated to the worship of a local deity and placed in selected locations on hilltops, mountain-sides, water springs and along main trails, are a specific mark of the culture and territorial presence of the populations which inhabited the Apennines, including the Sabines and the Picenes in the area of the Sibillini Mountain Range: «before the Roman conquest, the Sabines used to position their shrines in sites of strategical significance, mainly on the heights that overlooked the land below and by mountain passes» (Alessandra Romagnoli, *I santuari del distretto nursino durante l'età repubblicana in Nursia e l'ager Nursinus - Un distretto sabino dalla praefectura al municipium*, edited by Simone Sisani, 2013).

Highland shrines were also a sort of natural offspring which arised from the settlement model that those same populations, including the Sabines and Picenes, had been implementing across that same territories for centuries: a scattered pattern of 'vici' and 'pagi', small hamlets with some very limited

level of hierarchy, and a number of even smaller outposts set at significant positions along or by the main communication trails. In the Iron Age, «large number of small and even tiny highland shrines [were present in the area of Norcia], fully part of an economic, administrative and religious pattern which we know that existed in many areas of the Apennines, with relation to what is commonly defined as 'pagus/vicus system'» (Alexandra Stalinski, *Il paesaggio del sacro tra continuità e trasformazione in Nursia e l'ager Nursinus - Un distretto sabino dalla praefectura al municipium*, edited by Simone Sisani, 2013). A significant presence of highland shrines is also retrieved in the territories of the Picenes, a presence which is «closely linked to the non-urban character of the culture of the Picenes and is possibly connected to actual features, as the worship was to be devoted, in the first place, to natural events, among which the available documentation points to water springs and deities linked to livestock and agriculture» (Alessandro Naso, *Piceni - Storia e archeologia delle Marche in epoca preromana*, 2000).

Fig. 76 - Small bronze statues of warriors dating to the fifth century B.C. found in the votive deposit at the highland shrine of Ancarano of Norcia (Vatican Museums)

But highland shrines were also the expression of both the religious feelings and the emotional bond that the ancient populations of the Italian peninsula, especially along the Apennine mountainous ridge, preserved in their hearts for a territory so harsh, and yet so beloved. Religious feelings of piety, of devotion and worship, and of awe.

The territory of Norcia and its surrounding area have provided many instances of highland shrines, from Ancarano di Norcia to Valle Fuino, and then Monte Alvignano, Forma Cavaliere, Ocosce, Roccaporena, Collegiacone, Civita di Cascia, and many others. In today's Marche, many shrines have been found, though especially in the northern portion of today's province of Marche, in the lack of extensive excavation campaigns in the southern area bordering the Sibillini Mountain Range.

We must also consider that «our knowledge about the sites of worship in the area of Norcia before the arrival of the Romans is significantly partial, owing not only to the mountainous nature of the largest portion of this territory, but also because the available data originates from serendipitous finds [...] on which not even the most recent excavations allowed to cast more light» (Stalinski, op. cit.). And the same applies to the territory once inhabited by the Picenes.

So within the framework of our conjecture, which concerns the narrative origin of the legendary tales which live amid the Sibillini Mountain Range, we are supposing, as a reasonable hypothesis, that the Lake and Cave set on Mount Vettore and Mount Sibyl may have been considered, throughout the Iron Age, as highland shrines, which were possibly dedicated to the worship of some evil entity that was reputed to be in control, or be the cause, of the mighty earthquakes which struck the land on a recurrent basis. Otherworldly shrines, connected to natural landmarks, a Lake and a Cave, and to a very specific event, the fearful shaking of the mountains.

A possible objection to the above conjecture might be posed in the form of an observation of the sites where the two geographical landmarks are placed: if we look at the Lake and Cave set amid the Sibillini Mountain Range, and later known as Pilate's and Sibyl's, as potential highland shrines for the Sabines and Picenes, no remnants or wrecks of any shrine or temple has ever been found. Up there, no archeological evidence of the potential presence of a highland shrine has ever been retrieved.

However, as a matter of fact we can actually expect to find no remnants of any permanent, tangible fabric.

In the land of Sabines, highland shrines «only rarely are marked by fixed structures, that is an actual building for worship» (Stalinski, op. cit.). They «usually cannot be traced through the presence of a temple or small building [as] many sites of worship of the Sabines lack any permanent structures, so they are fated to leave no mark of their former existence. [...] Thus the most ancient sacred sites are not provided with monumental structures, but only with a temporary fabric, as the place in itself, immersed in a natural environment, is a manifestation of the deity which dwells in the nature [...] It is a religious sentiment of remarkable antiquity, in which the heritage of archaic animistic beliefs is visible: the god cannot be parted from the nature of the place where he/she manifests himself and in which he/she dwells; all this does not require the construction of a temple» (Romagnoli, op. cit.). The same happens in the area inhabited by the Picenes, in which «there is no evidence, as to the pre-Roman age, of architectural remains of shrines, but only of votive offerings, which have been found as single items or in troves» (Naso, op. cit.).

So nothing is left and almost nothing is to be found on Mount Vettore and Mount Sibyl, if any shrines have ever been set at the Lake and Cave, apart from the possible offerings we are going to detail later in the next paragraphs. No masonry, no roof tiles, no carved stones and decorations.

We must also note that any potential remnant would have been entirely wiped out and erased already centuries or even millennia ago: the bottom of the glacial cirque in which the Lake lies has been subject to a recurrent process of elevation, out of the recurrent landslides from the overhanging walls of rock, from which layers over layers of debris were cast into the waters; and the Cave has undergone a number of repeated collapses, partly due to earthquakes and partly to man's activity, in an attempt to close the cavern's mouth to unwanted necromancer and in the subsequent efforts to reopen it.

Therefore, at the present stage of our investigation we can only guess what sort of deity the men of the Iron Age may have intended to worship or summon at the Lake and Cave.

We can only stop ourselves, with humble, awe-stricken steps, at the very threshold of the antique legendary core of the otherworldly myth which lives at the very center of the Sibillini Mountain Range.

But is this true?

Actually, we may try to direct our guess at a more specific direction, by also taking into account our previous papers, *Sibillini Mountain Range: the legend before the legends* and *Sibillini Mountain Range, a cave and lake to the Otherworld*.

So let's make our entrance into the core of a legend: an Otherworld in central Italy, hidden amid the Italian Apennines.

6. *Otherworld: the legend's core*

6.1 *Demons of the earthquakes*

We are now facing the most hidden secret of the legendary tale which lives amid the Sibillini Mountain Range. Not a tale of Sibyls and Roman prefects, but of earthquakes. And terror.

To step further into the original core of the myth, we must go back to our previous papers, *Sibillini Mountain Range: the legend before the legends* and *Sibillini Mountain Range, a cave and lake to the Otherworld*.

In the listed papers, we investigated what we consider as the marks left by the original, native legend that seemed to inhabit the Sibillini Mountain Range: a legend whose true core was concealed by additional legendary layers, including a narrative on an Apennine Sibyl and a story on the cursed body of Pontius Pilate.

We found that the narratives concerning the Lake and the Cave share four remarkable common characters.

First, the two sites were believed to be inhabited by legendary demonic presences. Second, the two of them beheld the performance of necromantic rituals, also involving the summoning of local, mythical demons. Third, at both sites the disturbances stirred by necromancers were such that tempests and storms were raised, with devastating effects on the neighbouring land. Fourth, men seemed to believe that an access to some sort of Otherworld may exist at both the Lake and Cave, in the possible forms of a 'nekyia', the summoning of the shadows of the dead at the entrance of a gloomy realm, or as a 'katabasis', a journey which brings a mortal man through that passageway and into a land of dread.

We are now before the very core of the legend of the Sibillini Mountain Range. The most ancient myth, almost lost in the mists of the Iron Age.

We are about to the step into the hidden nucleus of this fascinating legendary tale, with the help of the conjecture we have proposed in the present paper as to the remarkable seismic nature of the Sibillini Mountain Range and the relation established by the local population with harrowing, devastating events.

We stress, again, the point that what we are now proposing is a conjectural scenario, though fully in line with our preceding research papers: further assumptions which are to be considered as guesses on an evanescent realm of dreams and credences that men and women may have housed in their hearts across the many centuries of the Iron age, before the arrival of the Romans.

We may suppose that the political and religious leaders that lived in the small hamlets which encircled the most elevated peaks of the Sibillini Mountain Range knew about the otherworldly character of both the Lake and Cave. The elderly possibly used to bequeath to the younger generations a collection of tales about their forefathers, who had been struck by the earthquakes and had heard the yell of the mountain. They had ascended the cliffs to implore the mercy of the mountain itself, where the demon lived. They knew that the fiendish being or beings resided in a Lake set amid the sheer walls of what we know today as Mount Vettore, They also knew that others believed that the Lake was not its dwelling, as according to a version of the legendary tradition the demonic presence inhabited the fearful Cave set on the peak of today's Mount Sibyl, not far from the Lake itself.

We may imagine that such were the narratives which were passed on from one generation to another as the centuries rolled by.

And when the earthquake struck again, it was the time to act.

A large, devastating blow hit the whole land, with its subsequent trail of harrowing secondary shocks. Or, smothered rumbles and vibrations began to come up from the ground, an ominous sign that destruction was about to come. In either case, the population in terror asked for protection. They wanted the earthquake to stop. And they asked their leaders to act accordingly.

Fig. 77 - The eastern profile of Mount Vettore ominously looming on the small hamlet of Pretare, in a picture taken before its total destruction following the seismic sequence of 2016

We may imagine that rulers and priests, in smaller or larger company, ascended the steep mountainsides to Mount Vettore or Mount Sibyl, or even both, in accordance to the specific credence being held by the local communities in that specific moment in their history, on the 'effectiveness' of each of the two sites as to the attainment of a standstill in the seismic activity. A preceding failure at the Lake would bring people to look at the Cave as a most successful place where to ask for mercy, while a new

success obtained by the icy waters set beneath the cliffs of Mount Vettore would shift the attention and hopes away from the cavern. At certain times, we may also imagine that the performance of rituals at both places was considered as necessary when pursuing an attempt at stopping the tremors.

What would they do, on their arrival at the Lake or Cave?

In our conjecture, the scope of their visit, which they certainly considered any less than appalling, was to establish a terrifying contact with the otherworldly being or beings that allegedly lived beneath the mountain. They wanted to communicate with them, and speak to them. They wanted to ask them to stop the earthquakes. For the salvation of their own lives and the lives of their families.

What sort of otherworldly beings may they expect to meet?

Of course, we have no idea of the name or names that were possibly attributed to him (or it, or them) across the centuries and by different local communities around the Sibillini Mountain Range. We don't even know how they may have figured them to be, in their mythical dreams. Sure enough, if our model is true, the legendary nature of such superhuman beings was not that of a propitious deity: most probably they were a sort of mythical demons or demonic gods or supernatural monsters, which resided in the very core of the Sibillini Mountain Range, perhaps surrounded by a sort of demonic court of additional, lesser fiends, which possibly, but this is a mere fancy, accounted for the smaller seismic shocks. We repute that a faint trace of all this still persists in the subsequent legendary tradition concerning the Sibillini Mountain Range, for which both the Lake and Cave are inhabited by a demonic presence, as detailed in our previous paper *Sibillini Mountain Range: the legend before the legends*.

So what the representative of the local community would do, on their arrival at the Lake or Cave?

When you get today to the Lake, set within the precipitous glacial cirque of Mount Vettore, or to the Cave, whose collapsed entryway stands on the solitary peak of Mount Sibyl encircled by vertical ravines, you are certainly impressed, and yet your mind and heart are full of the joyful enchantment typical of a tourist or hiker during a most pleasant excursion.

On the contrary, the men of the Iron Age were overwhelmed by sheer terror.

Fig. 78 - Eerie scenery at today's Lakes of Pilate

We must imagine a visit conducted in a most grievous predicament, possibly shortly after an earthquake strike of significant magnitude, with casualties and wrecked dwellings and new cracks torn in the mountains. Or even carried out in the expectancy of a great seismic blow, as the rumbles of a minor seismic sequence continued to frighten the land for days or weeks. In both cases, Mount Vettore and Mount Sibyl would be quivering and resounding as a ceaseless series of quakes proceeded to shake the Sibillini Mountain Range, even at the very moment of that ghastly visit.

Their hearts filled with dread, those men would try to get in touch with the fiendish deity beneath, by staging some kind of ritual.

In the framework of a highland shrine, the first and most probable action they may have been performing at the Lake or Cave is votive offering.

In the Sabine and Picene cultures, as in other ancient Appennine cultures, the highland shrine was mainly a cache, a deposit for ritual offerings presented by the worshipper to the local deity: «in the absence of permanent temples, the presence of a cult is made apparent by the discovery of votive deposits, in which the offered materials are similar to other finds retrieved in the territory of the Umbrians and Samnites, a token of a common culture and the expression of shared religious sentiment which marked the people of the Apennines» (Romagnoli, op. cit.).

Fig. 79 - Small bronze statues of worshipper dating to the fourth century B.C. found in the votive deposit at the highland shrine of Valle Fuino (National Archeological Museum of Umbria)

Votive offerings, cast into the Lake's water or the Cave's vestibule and inner pits, may have included small bronze statuettes, bronze and iron tools, ceramic vessels, typically found in deposits pertaining to the Sabine and Picene areas (Romagnoli, Riva, Naso, op. cit.).

However, owing to the specific, fiendish nature of the worshipped deity, that would not be enough. The leaders of the community could not just come back to their hamlets having cast a handful of small objects into the Lake or Cave, while the earthquakes continued to shake the whole land.

We can imagine that some additional rituals may have been performed by the two geographical landmark, in a more determined effort to establish a communication link with the merciless chthonian potency.

In the theatrical setting of the glacial cirque of Mount Vettore or the cliff of Mount Sibyl, ancient priests may have developed rituals aimed at the summoning of the legendary demonic entity. We can suppose that words were spoken, accompanied with gestures, in a sort of necromantic play intended to conjure up the demons of the earthquakes, but also designed to satisfy the demand for reassurance strongly expressed by the local communities, which could not be satisfied by the mere deposition of small offerings. Different rituals were possibly staged in different moments during the history of the local communities. Attempts of various sorts may have been put in place, according to the successful or unsuccessful results of the previous versions of the rituals, in terms of observed response in the earthquake's behaviour. We may also suppose that a remnant of this sort of ceremonies may have lingered in the subsequent tradition, with necromancy being performed at the Lake and Cave in later centuries, as illustrated in our previous paper *Sibillini Mountain Range: the legend before the legends*.

The presence of men, up there, was only temporary. Awe-stricken, after the completion of their rituals, they would run downhill with the utmost haste, leaving those sinister place to the shadows of the night. In some cases, they may have held a ritual vigil through the night, in the hope to establish a ghastlier contact with the fiendish entities which lived beneath the mountain.

Of course, the earthquake, as a natural event utterly unheeding of the efforts and hopes of human beings, did not mind at all the rituals being carried out by the fervent representatives of the local communities. In many occurrences, the seismic waves just went on steadily and undisturbed, to the full disappointment of the people who waited in the hamlets below.

Fig. 80 - The ridges leading down from the cliff of Mount Sibyl and to the hamlet of Montemonaco

In predicaments of particular terror, when the earthquake happened to smash the land with a most powerful might, we can also imagine that specific local communities, in a peculiar moment of their history, may have resorted to a much more extreme plea.

Of this, we have no evidence at the two sites, nor this practice has ever been part of the cultural tradition of the ancient populations of Italy, and of the Romans neither.

However, there are hints which seem to suggest that, at least in some rare, exceptional case, a most precious offering may have been presented to the

legendary fiendish demons in a final, almost desperate effort to stop the earthquakes.

It's human sacrifice. As we will see in the next paragraph.

6.2 Resorting to the ultimate sacrifice against the earthquake

We are exploring the fascinating conjecture that the Lake and Cave set amid the Sibillini Mountain Range might have been considered, throughout the Iron Age and up to the Roman conquest of the area, as highland shrines dedicated to some demons or demonic gods of the earthquakes.

We saw that it may be assumed as a reasonable possibility that rituals were performed by the Lake's waters and at the Cave's entrance or vestibule, in an attempt to placate the fury of the chthonian potency.

Fig. 81 - The Lakes of Pilate

However, it is clear to our contemporary understanding of natural events that no earthquake can ever be stopped by throwing small offerings into a lake or cave, or even by performing lively, yet useless, necromantic

performances at the same spots in an effort to summon the subterranean deities which supposedly inhabited the bowels of the Sibillini Mountain Range.

We can also imagine the excitement, the desperate hopes, the many disillusionments, the tragic disappointments, the sense of grievous frustration that might have seized the Sabines and Picenes as they experimented, as centuries rolled by, the effectiveness of the rituals performed by the Lake, or Cave, or both, according to each successful or unsuccessful attempt at obtaining protection for themselves and their families, as earthquakes continued to hit the land across the years, decades and centuries.

And, when the earthquake struck with its utmost might, as in modern times occurred in the years 1703 and 2016, and terror amid the people reached its utmost peak, it is conceivable that the local leaders may have resorted to an ultimate, most desperate chance.

A bargain with the demon. A human life. In exchange for the cessation of the seismic sequence.

Why are we introducing a new hypothesis, perhaps redundant and unnecessary, to a model which is already conjectural?

We must remember that the sacrifice of human lives in religious rituals is not a feature which is manifestly retrieved in the ancient cultures of Italy.

In the history of the ancient Romans, the single instances of human offerings are connected to the ritual killings of a pair of Greeks and a pair of Gauls, which took place in the Forum Boarium in the years 28 B.C., 261 B.C and 113 B.C., when Rome was facing deadly military threats by its enemies, be they Gauls or Carthaginians, and in the wake of the ensuing panic. However, this is a truly peculiar occurrence in Roman history, because «so far as we know [such events were] entirely new to their experience. [...] It was not a] sacrifice in terms of the normal Roman ritual [...] for according to the formal religious rules this killing was not a sacrifice» (Mary Beard et al., *Religions of Rome*, 1998). The sacrifice of human life in religious ceremonies was not part of the cultural horizon of ancient Rome.

As for the Etruscans, scholars are still debating whether that culture ever practiced human sacrifice, in the presence of controversial references in ancient sources and a number of archeological finds still under investigation. For the Sabines and Picenes, no relevant evidence has ever been found on the topic.

So why are we mentioning the possibility, unfrequent as it might have been, of a possible sacrifice of human lives by the Lake and Cave in the Sibillini Mountain Range?

Fig. 82 - Mount Sibyl

The reason is that a sort of literary fossil of it is found in a most famous excerpt which is retrieved in the *Reductorium Morale* by Petrus Berchorius (Pierre Bersuire), a French benedictine monk and abbot, who lived between 1290 and 1362. It is a most significant passage, which we illustrated in our previous papers *The Lake of Pilatus in an antique manuscript: Pierre Bersuire* and *A legend for a Roman prefect: the Lakes of Pontius Pilate*, because it is the most ancient reference ever retrieved in written literature on the Lake of Norcia and its demonic nature.

In this excerpt, Berchorius seems to go straight to the inner nucleus of the Lake's myth. And this nucleus is definitely dark:

«And about that lake the most horrifying thing is what follows: each year that town [Norcia] sends a single man, a living man, beyond the walls that encircle the lake, as an offering to the demons, who immediately and in full view tear apart and slaughter that man; and people say that if the town does not comply, the country would be razed by the storms. Every year the town selects a certain criminal, and sends him there to the demons as a tribute».

Fig. 83 - Human sacrifice at the Lake of Norcia as it appears in Petrus Berchorius' *Reductorium Morale* (manuscript Latin 16786, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 301v)

[In the original Latin text: «Est ergo istud ibi summe terribile, quia civitas illa omni anno unum hominem vivum pro tributo infra ambitum murorum iuxta lacum ad daemones mittunt, qui statim visibiliter illum hominem lacerant et consumunt, quod (ut aiunt) si civitas non facit, patria tempestatibus deperiret. Civitas ergo annuatim aliquem sceleratum eligit que pro tributo daemonibus illuc mittit»].

According to Berchorius, Norcia had the habit to sacrifice a human life in the lake nested beneath the cliffs of Mount Vettore, to appease some kind of demons which would reside in the lake itself - demons that would ravage the whole region if not annually fed with the soul of a man.

In our previous paper on Pierre Bersuire, we asked ourselves a number of questions. Was this just an unfounded tale? Was this ghastly narrative a mere lie? Did Berchorius have some special, unknown reason to spread around such a heinous rumour?

However, Petrus Berchorius is fully aware that the piece of information he himself is reporting has something odd and shady in it:

«I would never believe in such a tale, for I could not read anything about such a practice in any books, unless I myself hadn't heard so illustrious a bishop firmly report this account».

[In the original Latin text: «Istud autem quia alicubi non legi, nullatenus crederem, nisi a tanto episcopo firmiter asseri audivissem»].

As Berchorius noted, definitely no evidence of such a barbaric and inhuman practice exists at all in any known chronicle reporting details on the ancient history of Norcia, back to the High Middle Ages and even further back to the Roman conquest. Not the slightest trace.

The rumour that Petrus Berchorius reported in his *Reductorium Morale*, written in the fourteenth century, appears to be a sort of evanescent ghost. A ghastly fossil of events that had taken place a great number of centuries earlier. The grim recollection of horrific occurrences possibly dating back to the Iron Age, when terror unleashed its might on the antique populations of the Sibillini Mountain Range, in the form of devastating earthquakes. Before the Romans came, in the early third century B.C.

In the light of the conjecture we are developing in the present paper, Berchorius' passage could be a reference to human sacrifices carried out at the Lake, in a remote past, to appease the local demons of the earthquakes. Because, as Berchorius reports, «if the town [Norcia] does not comply, the country would be razed by the storms».

A grisly, blood-curdling past, which seems to come out from the mists of forgotten centuries to haunt the dreams of contemporary men.

We possibly retrieve another faint trace of such a cruel practice in another literary account, this time referred to the Sibyl's Cave. It is found in a work written by Pierre Crespet, also known as 'Crespetus', a French Celestinian monk (1543 - 1594) who had travelled across Italy to visit the monasteries of the Celestines (possibly including the one in Norcia). In his treatise *De la hayne de Satan et malins esprist contro l'homme*, published in Paris in 1590, he widely speaks about the Sibyl of Norcia, as we extensively reported in our previous article *Apennine Sibyl: the bright side and the dark side*.

Crespetus recounts a sinister occurrence, a criminal trial held in Paris against a self-styled sorcerer, who had been to Mount Sibyl in Italy:

«I don't intend to overlook a remarkable testimony drawn from a criminal trial held against a renowned magician whose name was Domenico Mirabelli, an Italian from Arpino, and his stepmother Marguerite Garnier, who were arrested in Mantua with their spellbooks that they were fetching to the Sibyls, the goddesses of sorcerers, to consecrate them so as to render their books more powerful».

[In the original French text: «Je ne veux obmettre un notable discours tiré d'un procès qui a esté fait d'un insigne magicien nommé Dominique Mirabille Italien natif d'Arpine & à sa belle mere Marguerite Garnier, qui furent apprehendez à Mante avec leur livres de magie qu'ils portoient aux Sibylles deesses des magiciens pour estre consacrez, à fin d'avoir plus d'effet»].

In this excerpt, which narrates of a gloomy necromantic setting, the evil magicians goes as far as to promise the sibilline powers to offer human lives in exchange for their forbidden arts (Livre I, Discours 15):

«For all the services they required, they obliged themselves to honour the Sibyls with the titles of Dames and Princesses, and to offer a soul to them every year, on the very same day of the consecration of their spellbooks, for all the time of their lives».

portassent nuyfance, & s'offroient par toutes
ces courtoisies par obligatiō faictes ausdictes
Sibylles qu'ils honoroient de titre de Dames
& Princeffes, de leur offrir vne ame tous les
ans au mesme iour que leursdits liures au-
roient esté consacrez tant qu'ils viuroient, à

Fig. 84 - Human sacrifice at the Sibyl's Cave as it appears in Pierre Crespet (Crespetus), *De la hayne de Satan et malins esprist contro l'homme* (Paris, 1590), p. 246

[In the original French text: «S'offroient par toutes ces courtoisies par obligation faictes ausdictes Sibylles qu'ils honoroient de titre de Dames & Princeffes, de leur offrir une ame tous les ans au mesme iour que leursdits livres auroient esté consacrez tant qu'ils vivoient»].

Again, a hideous sacrifice of human lives is offered to the demonic beings which live at the Cave in the Sibillini Mountain Range, a further possible trace of a practice dating back to two millennia earlier. And, even though this sort of barbaric gift may also be seen as a demonic bargain typical of black magic as practiced in much later times, like the Middle Ages and Renaissance, nonetheless we must note that the trait of land devastation, a token of earthquakes as we will see later, is fully present in Crespetus' description of the Sibyl's Cave:

«When the Sibyl is addressed, by magicians or others, tempests and lightings are unleashed horribly on the whole territory».

[In the original French text: «Quand on communique avec elle, soyt magicien ou autre, les tempestes & foudres s'esmouvent horriblement par tout le païs»].

So we are possibly before the inner core of the legendary tale which lives amid the Sibillini Mountain Range. A dark core, a narrative of earthquake and terrors and demons, also marked by faint signs of potential human sacrifices effected at the Lake or Cave, in a desperate, ultimate effort by the men of the iron Age to stop the fury of the seismic waves, possibly only in the wake of the most paroxysmal, destructive writhing of the earth.

We stress again the fact that the model we are building up is mainly a conjectural scenario, though based on the available literary tradition, the geographical and physical nature of the territory, and the history and culture of the populations which lived in the area before the Roman conquest.

However, we repute that the track we are treading is the a most interesting one. A track which leads to the otherwordly character of the Sibillini Mountain Range. As we will continue to see in the next paragraph.

6.3 The otherwordly character of the Lake and Cave

In the course of our long journey into the legendary tradition of the Sibillini Mountain Range, we have stumbled upon a significant number of references that seemed to point to an otherwordly character of both the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate.

In our previous paper *Sibillini Mountain Range, a cave and lake to the Otherworld* we have fully retraced, across the relevant literature, the many passages which are manifestly drawn from the antique tradition of otherwordly journeys: a test bridge of supernatural narrowness and magical ever-slamming doors as described in the account written by Antoine de la Sale on the Sibyl's Cave; the Lake of Pilate as an entrance to Hell in the excerpt drawn from Petrus Berchorius; the mythical resonances with Cumae, in the province of Campania, Italy, where a cave lying by the Lake Avernus provided a passageway to Hades, the realm of the dead, with the Cumaean Sibyl transplanted amid the Apennines by Andrea da Barberino in his romance *Guerrino the Wretch* and the Lake of Pilate identified as 'Avernus' in a sixteenth-century map; and further mythical affinities with Lough Derg, in County Donegal, Ireland, the abode of the Purgatory of St. Patrick, which opened its gate to the subterranean horrors, with *Guerrino the Wretch* sent by Andrea da Barberino straight into the Purgatory after his visit to the Sibyl, and with Antoine de la Sale's miniature of the entrance to the Cave strikingly similar to the many miniatures portraying the Purgatorial hollow.

In our perusal of the otherwordly literature from the *Odisyssey* to Aeneas, and then to the Christian visions of St. Paul and Pope St. Gregory I the

Great, and finally to the medieval descriptions of demons and fiendish punishments as described in the *Vision of St. Adamnán*, the *Vision of Tnúgdalus*, and the *Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii*, we found that the Cumaean Hades and the Irish Purgatory envisaged a category of journeys which can be considered as travels into the Otherworld par excellence: these are travels that are performed not in a mere vision, but in actual reality. With a man's physical body.

Because Cumae and Lough Derg were appalling fissures in the world of the living. Two cracks pierced in the continuity of our ordinary world, the world that God created for human beings. Two 'hot spots', two clefts, dreadfully opened to legendary physical visions of subterranean, chthonian Hells. At those two sites, living men could be so fool as to make an attempt at crossing the gates which must never be crossed. Two passageways to the Otherworld. Two entryways to an afterlife inhabited by legendary demonic powers.

Entryways whose presence was signalled by known landmarks, geographical features which were reputed to mark the presence of the two legendary 'hot spot': lakes and caves, at both sites. Landforms which fully identified the two sites on the surface of Earth, and were known as such. Landmarks to legends.

In the above paper, we conjectured that the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate, too, may have been considered, in an antique past, as legendary passageways to an Otherworld: a further entryway, a physical threshold, possibly even as antique as that of Cumae, which is no earlier than the foundation of the city, which took place in the eighth century B.C. (Lough Derg with its Purgatory is surely more recent, as it is basically a legend born in early Christianity).

Now, we are able to expand this conjecture with the further hypothesis we have been illustrating in the present paper: across the Iron Age, the local populations of Sabines and Picenes, stricken by terror under the pressure of recurrent, pervading earthquakes, possibly set highland shrines at both sites, in an attempt to appease the fiendish god which, in their view, certainly lived beneath the Sibillini Mountain Range.

So, the Lake and the Cave lying on Mount Vettore and Mount Sibyl were landmarks: geographical features which marked a point of access to an Otherworld.

An antique legendary tale, possibly dating as far back as the Iron Age. A credence concerning an entryway to a mythical Otherworld in central Italy. One of a most terrific, dreadful sort. A crevice in our world, opened in the mountainous ridges out of sheer terror. Terror for one own's life and for the fate of one's family. Terror for the ruin of one's land. Terror for the devastating might of the earthquakes.

Fig. 85 - The Lakes of Pilate as an otherwordly setting

In the above-mentioned paper, *Sibillini Mountain Range, a cave and lake to the Otherworld*, we asked ourselves the following questions: what sort of dreadful dream did men conceive at the Lake and Cave set amid the mountains of the central Apennines? What sort of Otherworld was this?

We have now provided a conjectural, significant answer to the first question. Possibly the dream that men in a long-gone past dreamt about the Sibillini Mountain Range was about earthquakes and demons.

But what about the second question? What sort of Otherworld was being imagined by those ancient people?

Certainly this otherworldly fancy was different from the afterlives which were reputed to be accessible by men from Cumae and Lough Derg. People did not ascend the steep versants of the Sibillini Mountain Range to penetrate into a Hades or Purgatory, full of the shades of mortals or resounding with the harrowing screams of purgatorial souls.

Down there, beneath the huge, impressive mountainous fastenances, some sort of hellish den housed a great demon or demons, which were able to shake the mounts from their very roots. The house of the fiendish being or beings were hollows and caverns set beneath the rock, unattainable places that no living man would ever wish to visit.

Fig. 86 - The collapsed entrance to the Sibyl's Cave as it is today,

Within the framework of the conjectural model we have been defining in the present paper, we can suppose that the local communities did not consider the Lake and Cave as entryways to such Otherworld, but rather as points of contact with the otherworldly, chthonian powers.

The purpose of the visits to the two 'hot spots' was to establish a communication with the demonic entities which presided over the earthquakes.

They did not intend to physically pass into the Otherworld in which the appalling deities lived their abominable life. They could not have made any successful entrance through the Lake, which of course did not offer any threshold to cross, if not by drowning; some of them, more foolhardy than their companions, might have made attempts at venturing into the darkness of the Cave, but their return would have proven to be utterly uncertain, as the many vertical pits possibly awaiting the visitor in the gloomy cavern were fully able to bestow sudden death to any bold visitor.

Nonetheless, in the envisaged conjecture the Lake and Cave were positively otherworldly sites. There, human beings could stand in front of the dwelling of a demon, within precipitous wall of sheer rock or on an eerie mountain-top, separated by a titanic crown from the world below.

An Otherworld that men faced not in the form of a 'katabasis', a journey which brings a mortal man through that passageway and into a land of gloom, but rather as a 'nekyia', the summoning of otherworldly entities, be they the shadows of the dead or, as in this specific case, a fiendish demon, at the entrance of the gloomy realm.

An otherworldly character that will mark the two sites set amid the Sibillini Mountain Range for the subsequent millennia, so that all the additional legendary narratives that will later settle on the Lake and Cave, with their Sibyls and roman prefects, will bear the faint, indistinct, shadowy stamp of a demonic Otherworld.

6.4 The ancient Otherworld consigned to oblivion

With the arrival of the Romans in the territory of the 'Tetricus Mons' the history of the two otherworldly sites set amid the Sibillini Mountain Range, the Lake and the Cave, changes altogether.

Roman troops led by consul Manius Curius Dentatus sweep through the land in the year 290 B.C. In the subsequent years the Picenes, too, are brought under the political and administrative influence of Rome.

With the advent of a new, different administration of the region and local populations, highland shrines begin to tread an inexorable path leading to decline and extinction:

«With the advent of Rome, at the beginning of the third century B.C., this 'landscape of sacred sites' changes its shape. [...] Many small shrines appear to be subject to neglect. [...] This is certainly in line with the strategy of conquest and 'pacification' of the great city which [...] made use of different methods for the control of the conquered territories, inspired to a 're-shaping of local economy and public life' so as to reduce the level of strategic risk. In addition to the planned improvement of roads, it was of the utmost importance to concentrate the local population, moving the people from the 'dangerous' (in Rome's opinion) settlements in the highlands to the new attractive poles, easier to control, and at the same time proposing the emotional image of wealthy, modern, friendly Rome» (Stalinski, op. cit.).

Fig. 87 - Roman Norcia: votive stones with figures of Dionysus and Bacchae dating to the first century A.D. (Museum of the Criptoportico, Norcia)

It was a deliberate process which led to the «gradual decline of the ancient sites of worship, following the advent of the Roman age. The sites were not immediately abandoned, yet their importance as points for the control of the territory and sites of aggregation ceased altogether, to the advantage of the new sites that were selected by the Romans as administrative poles» (Romagnoli, op. cit.).

So, if any highland shrines have ever been set at our Lake and Cave, as we conjectured in the present article, they slowly vanished from history as the policies and culture of the new conquerors, the Romans, strengthened their hold on the Sabines and Picenes, who underwent a significant process of assimilation, with «a sort of slow 'seduction by Rome's culture and way of life'», so that «we can confidently imagine that the ancient highland shrines, too, were gradually abandoned, in the absence of any dramatic circumstances» (Stalinski, op. cit.).

It has also been noted that «in a landscape substantially deprived of large settlements, as in the territory of Norcia before the arrival of the Romans, it is infrequent the retrieval of structures pertaining to a site of worship, unless it had acquired a new role in the administrative policy of Rome, preserving itself though with a different appearance following Roman assimilation».

The Lake and Cave, with their legendary demons of the earthquakes, had no place in the new cultural, political and administrative system implemented under the rule of Rome.

Any precarious structures that may have been present there, if any, were just washed away by the rains, snows, winds and, finally, the collapses caused by the same earthquakes to which the shrines were dedicated. And certainly the Romans did not add nor build any new structures at the two sites.

So the Sibillini Mountain Range gradually cancelled the very memory of its mythical fiendish presence, heinous demons which an antique legend considered as the originators of the devastating earthquakes who used to hit the area on a recurrent basis.

Throughout the glorious history of Rome, no trace remained of the dreadful myth dating back to the Iron Age. In the Middle Ages, no mention is available on a Lake and a Cave set in the central Apennines, in Italy, with their mythical charge and otherwordly marks.

We must get to the fourteenth century and Petrus Berchorius to catch a new glimpse of the surviving tradition that still seemed to linger amid the Sibillini Mountain Range. This tradition had been running across hidden trails, concealed paths, possible threads of oral narratives, totally unregistered on the parchment of manuscripts, until it exploded again, as a firework in a moonless night, at the beginning of the fifteenth century, with the amazing work written by Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de la Sale.

But, at that time, the legendary narrative was already contaminated by other legendary tales, coming from far-off countries: the Apennine Sibyl, an offspring of the Matter of Britain, and Pontius Pilate, another northern-European legend.

6.5 Storms and devastation over the land

In the legendary tradition of the Lake of Pilate and the Sibyl's Cave, a specific trait is found that has always puzzled scholars and researchers.

In our previous paper *Sibillini Mountain Range: the legend before the legends*, we retraced the presence of a number of references to this peculiar aspect in the vast literary production concerning the Lake and the Cave, and we classified this particular trait as a common, shared feature which appears in both the Apennine Sibyl's and Pilate's legendary narratives, as one of the original traits which seemed to mark the most antique nucleus of the myth which inhabits the Sibillini Mountain Range, just like demons, necromancy, and a general otherwordly character.

With the elaboration of the conjecture we have been setting down in the present article, we have outlined a mythical framework which provides a satisfactory explanation to the three common features listed above: across the Iron Age, rituals were possibly performed at the Lake and Cave in order

to appease legendary demonic entities which were believed to preside over earthquakes.

Time has come now to justify the presence of the fourth common aspect, too: tempests and destruction arising from the Lake and Cave.

We find references to it almost everywhere in the literature which concerns the Lake of Pilate. As we already saw, Petrus Berchorius, in his *Reductorium Morale*, written in the fourteenth century, reports that «each year that town [Norcia] sends a single man, a living man, beyond the walls that encircle the lake, as an offering to the demons, who immediately and in full view tear apart and slaughter that man; and people say that if the town does not comply, the country would be razed by the storms». Antoine de la Sale, in his fifteenth-century *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, writes that «that island [a rocky boulder set at the center of the Lake] is strictly guarded and protected by the local people on the ground that when anybody comes to it covertly and performs the art of the Fiend, after the operation is made a storm so violent raises in the region that all crops and goods in the country get spoiled». Fazio degli Uberti, in his fourteenth-century *Dittamondo*, writes that «here [at the Lake] Simon the Sorcerer ascends to consecrate his spellbook - so that troublesome tempests are aroused - according to what local people say». Arnold von Harff, a German knight, reports that «when this happened [necromancy was performed at the Lake] the water of this little lake was swept up into a cloud and descended in a thunderstorm, flooding all the land for three or four miles around, so that that year was no corn there». And, as to the Sibyl's Cave, Pierre Crespet, the French Celestinian monk we already mentioned in a previous paragraph, reported that «when the Sibyl is addressed, by magicians or others, tempests and lightings are unleashed horribly on the whole territory».

Fig. 88 - The words «tempest» and «stormy clouds» recurrently appearing in the literature concerning the Lake of Pilate and the Sibyl's Cave, from the works by Petrus Berchorius, Antoine de la Sale, Fazio degli Uberti, Arnold von Harff and Pierre Crespet (refer to the paper *Sibillini Mountain Range: the legend before the legends* for a full reference to the relevant manuscripted and printed sources)

The reason and nature of such odd tempests were also matter of puzzled debate amid scholars many centuries ago. A note to the work of Fazio degli Uberti, contained in a fifteenth-century manuscript and added by a scribe, Andrea Morena from Lodi, specifies that «the lake [...] is visited by those who perform the art of necromancy to consecrate their spellbooks, so that for this reason the region is troubled by scourge and famine or other afflictions». In 1550 the dominican friar Leandro Alberti, in his work *Descrittione di tutta l'Italia*, wrote that «... the Lake of Norcia, of which unlearned people believe demons swim in it, for they repeatedly see the waters raise and lower in a way that this vision amazes those who behold the lake, as it appears to be an eerie occurrence, being veiled the reason for this motion [...] It is certainly true that if we diligently look for the reason for the said motion, we clearly see that it is the wind, which unceasingly urges the waters across the small lake surrounded by high cliffs, and owing to this urge the waters are seen to alternatively raise and lower, to the greatest amazement by the beholders». And Antonio Giovanni Magini, an Italian scientist and geographer, in his edition of Ptolemy's "Geography" published in 1617, includes the following remark:

Fig. 89 - The reference to the Lake of Norcia from Antonio Giovanni Magini's edition of Ptolemy's *Geography* (Arnhem, 1617), p. 122

«On a certain mountain of the Apennines, which is called Mount Vettore, the Lake of Norcia stands, whose waters are seen swelling and then subsiding ceaselessly, to the utmost wonder of the beholders, so that naive people believe that there demons dwell and can be queried».

[In the original Latin text: «Est in iugo quoque Apennini montis, quod Mons Victor vocatur, Lacus Nursinus, cuius aquae perpetuis motibus salire, vicissimque subsidere cernuntur, non sine magna admiratione, unde ibi cacodaemones inhabitare vocatosque responsa dare imperitum vulgus putat»].

In 1653, Father Fortunato Ciucci, another Celestinian monk, wrote his *Chronicles of the antique town of Norsia*, in which he reported on the sinister events taking place at the Lake:

«This was ascertained by the people in Norcia, who reported that they many times had found such necromantic items by the Lake [...], and by this reason sometimes large damages used to occur in town out of the hail and thunderbolts which fell from above. [... The] damage caused by storms and hail and thunderbolts which ensued when Wizards came to the lake and performed their abominable arts».

[In the original Italian text: «Questo si verifica dagli uomini di Norcia, i quali testificavano di aver più volte trovato queste ed altre cose simili vicino al Lago [...], per causa de' quali alle volte soleva accadere gran danno alla Città per le molte grandini, e saette che dall'aria piombavano. [...Il] danno dalle tempeste dalle grandini, e folgori che ne succedevano quando qualche Mago ivi si approssimava, e metteva in opra l'esecranda dottrina»].

In the subsequent centuries, this peculiar piece of information continued to be largely disregarded by the scholars as some sort of fairy tale being reported by the local populace, while the attention was mainly directed to the Cave and its legendary Sibyl rather than the nearby Lake with its Roman prefect and troubled waters. Only, Arturo Graf, an Italian man of letter and professor, confronted with the Lake in his comprehensive *Myths, legends and superstitions of Middle Ages*, published in 1893, in which he linked the turmoils to the ancient legendary narratives about Pontius Pilate, whose cursed body, when thrown into the Tiber, the Rhône and other

tentative burial places, was rejected with great agitation of demons (see also our previous papers *Sibillini Mountain Range: the legend before the legends* and *A legend for a Roman prefect: the Lakes of Pontius Pilate*).

There is no doubt on the fact that the Sibillini Mountain Range, as a ridge which separates territories that overlook two different seas, the Adriatic and the Tyrrhenian, is prone to significant weather changes and subject to the action of strong winds and intense storms, as local residents can report. And, certainly, extreme events may occur in the highlands, where the crests of Mount Vettore and the other elevated cliffs, including Mount Sibyl, are fully exposed to the rage of the elements, so that hikers often find themselves endangered in case they are caught on their way along the highland trails during a tempest.

And this was no different in previous centuries. Giovanni Battista Lalli, a poet from Norcia who lived in the seventeenth century, had a first-hand experience of this same occurrence, as he himself wrote in his poem *Gerusalemme Desolata (Ruined Jerusalem)* (Canto II, 48):

Fig. 90 - Tempest over Mount Sibyl from Giovanni Battista Lalli's *Gerusalemme desolata* (Milano, 1630), p. 141

«And if anyone unwelcomed dares to draw too near,
and she chooses to deny herself to him,
in various manners he repels him
from his venturesome design.
Sometimes she fills the sky with gloomy clouds carrying the rain,
so that a horrible storm comes to life;
sometimes with a mortal threat, any mercy dispelled,
she unleashes the savage beasts against the wayfarer».

[in the original Italian text:
E se quivi appressarsi alcun s'accinge,
Ch'à lei no piaccia, e d'introdur no'l degna;
Con diverse maniere il risospinge
Da quell'impresa, che tentar disegna.
D'atre, e gravide nubi hor l'aria cinge,
Che ria tempesta à partorir ne vegna;
Hor minacciosa, ogni pietà sbandita,
Contro di quel l'horrende belve irrita.]

A further example is reported by Marcella Arca Petrucci, a professor at the University of Rome Tre, who quotes from a manuscripted plea written at the end of the seventeenth century by Giuseppe Pasqua, a priest of the small parish of Castelluccio di Norcia (Marcella Arca Petrucci, *La montagna di Norcia tra XVI e XVII secolo e le sue diverse rappresentazioni*, in *Rappresentazioni e pratiche della spazio in una prospettiva storico-geografica*, 1995). In it, Pasqua lamented the wintry, erratic, utterly dangerous weather which was to be experienced under the shadow of Mount Vettore, on the Pian Grande,

«[... Here at Castelluccio we have] hail, snow, fogs, frost and tempests and storms, so unpredictable that nobody can trustfully deem himself safe at a given time and still safe the very next hour; for this reason [...] wayfarers were found dead in the countryside, and big and small cattle as well. [...] In September 1686] a storm so violent hit the land, and it was so full of thunderbolts, lightnings, wind, rain, hail and snow, that the shepherds were forced to abandon their cattles [...] as if the whole world was about to collapse; it lasted a full day and night, and a thousand sheep died. [...] Everybody can see what sort of dangers use to fall on the poor hamlet of Castelluccio [... We can only] raise prayers to God lest this happens again».

[In the original Italian text: «[... Qui hanno luogo] grandini, nevi, nebbie, brine e tempeste de' temporali che niuno può assicurarsene da un'ora all'altra per il che si sono [...] trovati morti nella campagna viandanti e bestiami grossi e minuti. [...] Nel settembre 1686] successe un temporale così fiero di tuoni, lampi, saette, vento, acqua, grandine e neve che fu necessario abbandonare il bestiame [...] che pareva si volesse subissare il mondo e che durò un giorno e una notte e che morissero da un migliaro di pecore. [...] Si veda in che pericoli è sottoposto il povero Castelluccio [... Possiamo solamente] pregare Iddio che mai più succeda»].

Fig. 91 - Stormy weather on the Sibillini Mountain Range as seen from the peak of Mount Sibyl

However, all this is not enough to explain the eerie fame of the Lake and Cave, and the tempests unleashed over Norcia and the whole land. Many other Italian areas, marked by the presence of elevated peaks or ridges, both in the Apennines and the Alps, present the very same behaviour in terms of recurrent, violent storms, with fast-changing weather.

There must be something more to it.

And, in the light of the conjectures we have introduced in the present paper, we repute that the keyword to the true origin of the peculiar tempests connected to the Lake of Pilate and the Sibyl's Cave may possibly be the same: earthquakes.

6.6 The earthquakes which arise from the subterranean winds

In the legendary tradition of the Sibillini Mountain Range, winds and tempests are not just natural winds and tempest.

As we stated in the previous paragraph, there is more to it.

A first hint to the special character of winds in this magical context is provided to us by that same Pierre Crespet from whom we quoted passages about the Sibyl's Cave, drawing from his *De la hayne de Satan et malins esprist contro l'homme*, published in 1590.

As we already noted in our previous article *Sibillini Mountain Range: the legend before the legends*, Crespetus adds an additional reference to the magical, divine quality of such tempests and winds (Livre I, Discours 6):

«Heavenly Gods or maybe the stars themselves send those winds
Often it happens that when a Wizard wants to find treasures hidden beneath
the ground
or consecrate his spellbook
or by a sorcerous ritual subjugate some god to his will,
I heard that winds raise, and sudden storms».

[In the original Latin text:

«Hos ventos vel Dij aerij vel sydera mittunt,
Sepae etenim cum thesauros tellure latentes,
Vult auferre Magus vel consecrare libellum,
Vel magico ritu quemquam sibi subdere divum,
Audiui exortum ventum, subitamque procellam»].

peſtes & foudres ſeſmoũuét horriblemét par
 tout le païs, & afin qu'õ ne péſe cecy eſtre fa- Palyngeni-
 buleux. Palyngenius Poète Italien liu. 11. où il ^{nims.}
 parle de l'Equateur en fait mention quand il
 dit.

*Hos ventos vel Dij ærij vel ſydera mittunt,
 Sepæ erenim cùm theſauros tellure latentes,
 Vult auferre Magus vel conſecrare libellam,
 Vel magico ritu quemquam ſibi ſubdere diuum.*

*Audui exortum ventum, ſubitâque procellam
 Aut ſata ſtrauiſſe aut hærentes vitibus vnas.*

Fig. 92 - Magical winds from Pierre Crespet (Crespetus), *De la hayne de Satan et malins esprist contro l'homme* (Paris, 1590), p. 93

This suggestion, which Crespetus draws from a sixteenth-century work, the *Zodiacus Vitæ*, written by Marcellus Palingenius Stellatus in 1536, confirms a potential interpretation of the storms and ensuing devastations as something different from a mere weather disturbance, though severe as it may be.

And such winds are not related only to necromantic arts, for Palingenius, in his poem, adds the following words (Liber XI, *Aquarius*):

«Know then that innumerable, immense caverns
 lay beneath the earth; and when there fierce winds
 are generated, then they rouse savage
 battles, smite the earth, and with extraordinary fury
 they gather and overturn every town with their ramparts,
 until at some spot they erupt as a multitude, and
 disperse themselves in the air as blows of wind
 which finally vanish in peace [...]
 So are the troubled winds, which inhabit the subterranean abodes
 of the shades of the dead, who dwell in the darkness of caves».

[In the original Latin text:

«Scire igitur licet, innumeras vastasque cavernas
 Sub terris esse, atque illic quandoque creari
 Ingentes ventos; qui dum crudelia miscent

Proelia, concutiunt terram, nimioque furore
 Congressi evertunt totas cum moenibus urbes.
 Donec parte aliqua erumpant facto agmine, et auras
 diffusi in vacuas non longa pace quiescant. [...]
 Hos agitant ventos, qui subterranea regna
 Dij manes habitant, caecisque morantur in antris.»].

Fig. 93 - Chthonian winds from *Zodiacus Vitae* by Marcellus Palingenius Stellatus (edition printed in Basel, 1537, p. 362-363)

Because winds are mythically linked to earthquakes.

The connection between storms and seismic waves is not a concept developed in the sixteenth century by Palingenius. Actually, it represents a most antique, prescientific explanation on the origin of earthquakes.

It is around the year 340 B.C. that Aristotle, the great philosopher of ancient Greece, elaborates his comprehensive treatise *Meteorologica*, the first written essay on the parts of the earth and the universe, the elements of

which the world is composed, and the origin of natural events, including earthquakes.

According to Aristotle (*Meteorologica*, Book II, Part VIII), the shaking of the earth is caused by «the wind which we call an earthquake. [...] When the wind is present in sufficient quantity there is an earthquake». For the Greek philosopher, «the earth is spongy and cavernous», so that «the severity of the earthquake is determined by the quantity of wind and the shape of the passages through which it flows. Where it is beaten back and cannot easily find its way out the shocks are most violent, and there it must remain in a cramped space like water that cannot escape». Because when «a great wind is compressed into a smaller space and so gets the upper direction, [...] then breaks out and beats against the earth and shakes it violently».

Fig. 94 - The sentence «the wind which we call an earthquake» [«τὸν ἀνεμόν, ὃν καλοῦμεν σεισμόν»] which appears in Aristotle's *Meteorologica*, from *Aristotelis Opera edidit Academia Regia Borussica*, edited by August Immanuel Bekker (Berlin, 1831), Vol. I, p. 368, Bekker numbering 368a10-11

Earthquakes and winds. Winds which circulate beneath the ground, across huge, unseen hollows that pierce the earth underneath. And when the pressure of the winds becomes unbearable, the earth is shaken and beaten and struck. It is an earthquake.

Furthermore, when the underground winds erupt, a devastating storm occurs:

«The countries that are spongy below the surface are exposed to earthquakes because they have room for so much wind. [...] It has been known to happen that an earthquake has continued until the wind that caused it burst through the earth into the air and appeared visibly like a hurricane».

Fig. 95 - The sentence on earthquakes and hurricanes which appears in Aristotle's *Meteorologica*, from *Aristotelis Opera edidit Academia Regia Borussica*, edited by August Immanuel Bekker (Berlin, 1831), Vol. I, p. 366, Bekker numbering 366b31-33

Earthquakes and winds, then turning into storms. Such is the intimate connection which, in antiquity, was believed to exist between seismic events, devastation of the land, and tempests. A connection that will mark the legendary tale of the Sibillini Mountain Range for its whole history.

Aristotle's model will be adopted and extended by Titus Lucretius Carus, the great Roman philosopher and poet, who lived in the first century B.C. In his poem *De rerum natura* (*On the nature of things*), he describes with poetical, fascinating words the hollows which lie beneath the surface of the earth (Book VI, vv. 535-539 and 557-564):

«Now come the Earthquake's causes learn: and first
Conceive the Earth as on its surface seen,
So constituted is in depths below;
Hence, in its bosom holds vast windy caves,
Innumerable lakes, chasms, and pools profound,
With rocks abrupt, and cliffs precipitous [...]
When winds pent up in hollow depths
Bear to one part with shouldering violence,
They forceful heave the cavern's domed roof,

Till Earth gives way where the prone winds impend.
 Then lofty buildings on the surface reared,
 The more toward heaven they lift aspiring heads,
 The more, bulging and forced awry they yield,
 And started beams impend prepared to fall».

De terremotu
 Nunc age que ratio terremotibus extet
 Percipe. & in primis terras fac ut esse rearis
 Subter item & super uentis undiq; plenam.
 Speluncis multosq; lacus multasq; lacunas
 In gremio gerere: & rupes de rupes diruptaq; saxa

Praeterea uentus cum per loca sub caua terrae
 Conlectus parte ex una procumbit: & urgit
 Obnixus magnis speluncas uiribus altas
 Incumbit: quo uenti prona premit uis
 Tum supra terram que sunt extincta domorum
 Ad caelum que magis quanto sunt edita queque.
 Inclinata minent in eadem prodita partem a a i i q.
 Protraesteq; trabes impident ira; paratae

Fig. 96 - The verses on winds and earthquakes from Titus Lucretius Carus' *De rerum natura* (from a precious edition printed in Verona in 1486), p. 174-175

[In the original Latin text:
 «Nunc age, que ratio terremotibus extet
 Percipe. et in primis terram fac ut esse rearis
 Subter item ut super ventis undique plenam.
 Speluncis multosque lacus multasque lacunas
 In gremio gerere et rupes diruptaque saxa; [...]
 Praeterea ventus cum per loca sub cava terrae
 Conlectus parte ex una procumbit et urgit
 Obnixus magnis speluncas viribus altas,

Incumbit quo venti prona premit vis.
Tum supra terram que sunt extincta domorum
Ad caelum que magis quanto sunt edita queque.
Inclinata minent in eadem prodita partem
Protractaeque trabes impendent irae paratae»].

With great dramatic force, Lucretius depicts the terrifying effects of earthquakes, as generated by the subterranean winds, on the artifacts on men (vv. 570-576):

«Now because those winds
Blow back and forth in alternation strong,
And, so to say, rallying charge again,
And then repulsed retreat, on this account
Earth oftener threatens than she brings to pass
Collapses dire. For to one side she leans,
Then back she sways; and after tottering
Forward, recovers then her seats of poise.
Thus, this is why whole houses rock, the roofs
More than the middle stories, middle more
Than lowest, and the lowest least of all».

Fig. 97 - The verses on winds and earthquakes from Titus Lucretius Carus' *De rerum natura* (from a precious edition printed in Verona in 1486), p. 175

[In the original Latin text:
«Nunc quia respirant alternis inque gravescunt
Et quasi conlecti redeunt ceduntque repulsi,
Saepius hanc obrem minutatur terra ruinatur.
Quam facit; inclitus enim retroque recellat
Et recipit pro lapsa suas in pondere sedes.

Hac igitur rartione vacillant omnia tecta,
Summa magis mediis, media imis, ima per hilum»].

Again, the earthquakes are mighty commotions of the earth produced by the circulation of winds underneath, in the ghastly caverns concealed beneath the feet of men, and that no men has ever seen.

But earthquakes can become even more destructive when the winds find their way out of the earth, and plague the world above (vv. 577-584 and 591-600):

«Another cause of fearful tremblings is
When some tornado coming from without,
Or sprung in some dark subterranean mine,
Rushes to hollow places of the earth
And with wild tumult raves her caves among;
Till forceful whirling, bursting forth at length
In hideous yawnings, rends the founded Earth. [...]
Even when such prisoned winds fail to burst forth,
They rush through veins of Earth, and tremblings come,
As shudderings oft over shivering members creep.
How then do smitten populations quake
With terrors overhead, terrors beneath
Their feet, lest caverns crumbled up should open
Sudden wide jaws, engulfing ruins round».

[In the original Latin text:

«Est haec eiusdem quoque magni causa tremoris.
ventus ubi atque animae subito vis maxima quedam
aut extrinsecus aut ipsa tellure coorta
in loca se cava terra coniecit ibique
speluncas inter magnas fremit ante tumulto
vesabundaque portatur post incita cum vis
exagitata foras erumpitur et simul altam
diffidens terram magnum concinnat hiatum. [...]
Quod nisi prorumpit tamen impetus ipse animai
et fera vis venti per crebra foramina terrae
disperitur ut horror et incutit inde tremorem.
frigus ut in nostros poenitus qum venit in artus

concutit in viros cogens tremere atque movere.
 ancipiti trepidant igitur terrore per urbis.
 tecta superne timent, inferne [metuunt] cavernas
 terra ne dissolvat natura repente,
 neu distracta suum late dispendat hiatum
 idque suis confusa velit complere ruinis».

Fig. 98 - The verses on winds and earthquakes from Titus Lucretius Carus' *De rerum natura* (from a precious edition printed in Verona in 1486), p. 175-176

In the year 63 A.D., it is Lucius Annaeus Seneca, the illustrious philosopher who was tutor to Emperor Nero, who further develops the antique theoretical framework on the origin of seismic events. In his *Naturales quaestiones* he dedicates a full, extensive chapter to earthquakes.

After proposing a detailed summary of the opinions held by his Greek and Latin predecessors, Seneca illustrates his own view of the reason for which earthquakes are unleashed (Book VI, Chapter XVIII):

«The chief cause of earthquake, therefore, is air, an element naturally swift and shifting from place to place. As long as it is not stirred, but lurks in a vacant space, it reposes innocently, giving no trouble to objects round it. But when any cause coming upon it from without rouses it, or compresses it, and drives it into a narrow space, in the first instance, to be sure, it merely retires and roams about its enclosure. But when opportunity of escape is cut off, and resistance meets it on all hands, then 'with deep murmur of the mountain - It roars around the barriers' [a verse from vergil's "Aeneid", editor's note] which, after long battering, it dislodges and tosses on high, growing the more fierce, the stronger the obstacle with which it

has contended. By and by, when it has traversed the whole space in which it was enclosed, and has failed to find a way of escape, it recoils from the side on which its impact was greatest. It is then either distributed through the secret openings which the earthquake of itself causes here and there, or escapes through a new rent. So uncontrollable is this mighty power. No bolt can imprison wind».

[In the original Latin text: «Maxima ergo causa est, propter quam terra moveatur, spiritus natura citus, et locum e loco mutans. Hic quamdiu impellitur, et in vacanti spatio latet, iacet innoxius, nec circumiectis molestus est. Ubi illum extrinsecus superveniens causa sollicitat compellitque et in arctum agit, scilicet adhuc, cedit tantum et vagatur. Ubi erepta discedendi facultas est, et undique obsistitur, tunc 'magno cum murmure montis Circum claustra fremit', quae diu pulsata convellit ac iactat; eo acrior quo cum valentiore mora luctatus est. Deinde cum circa perlustravit omne quo tenebatur, nec potuit euadere, inde, quo maxime impactus est, resilit; et aut per occulta dividitur, ipso terraemotu raritate facta, aut per novum vulnus emicuit. Ita eius vis tanta non potest cohiberi, nec ventum tenet ulla compages»].

Fig. 99 - The passage on earthquakes and winds from Lucius Annaeus Seneca's *Naturales quaestiones* (from an edition printed in Venice in 1643), p. 203-204

So, in the opinion expressed by Seneca, earthquakes and winds are closely connected (Book VI, Chapter XXIV and XXV):

«I shall be ready to allow that air is the cause of this calamity. [...] When air has completely filled a large vacant space within the earth, and has begun to struggle and meditate escape, it lashes again and again the sides of the enclosure within which it lurks, and right over which, as it happens, cities are sometimes situated. The shaking is at times so violent that buildings standing above the area of disturbance are thrown down».

[In the original Latin text: «Spiritus esse huius mali causam et ipse consentio. [...] Cum spiritus magna vi in vacuum terrarum locum penitus applicuit, coepitque rixari, et de exitu cogitare, latera ipsa intra quae latet, saepius percutit, supra quae urbes interdum site sunt, haec nonnumquam adeo concutiuntur, ut aedificia superposita procumbant»].

Fig. 100 - Winds as generators of earthquakes from Lucius Annaeus Seneca's *Naturales quaestiones* (from an edition printed in Venice in 1643), p. 211-212

In the second half of the first century, Pliny the Elder, the philosopher and navy commander who died on the shore of Herculaneum during the catastrophic eruption of Mount Vesuvius, adhered to the conjecture that Aristotle, Lucretius and Seneca had endorsed (*Naturalis historia*, Book II, Chapter LXXXI):

«I certainly conceive the winds to be the cause of earthquakes. [...] For the trembling of the earth resembles thunder in the clouds; nor does the yawning of the earth differs from the bursting of the lightning; the enclosed air struggling and striving to escape».

[In the original Latin text: «Ventos in causa esse non dubium reor. [...] neque aliud est in terra tremor quam in nube tonitruum. Nec hyatus aliud quam cum fulmen erumpit incluso spiritu luctante et ad libertatem exire nitente»].

Fig. 101 - Earthquakes and winds from Pliny the Elder's *Naturalis historia* (from the first printed edition, Venice, 1469), p. 20

From his words, it really seems that Pliny may have had a direct experience of the occurrences associated to seismic events, even though he surely conducted his own investigations (Book II, Chapter LXXXII):

«A terrible noise precedes and accompanies the shock; sometimes a murmuring, like the lowing of cattle, or like human voices, or the clashing of arms. This depends on the substance which receives the sound, and the shape of the caverns or crevices through which it issues; it being more

shrill from a narrow opening, more hoarse from one that is curved, producing a loud reverberation from hard bodies, a sound like a boiling fluid from moist substances, fluctuating in stagnant water, and roaring when forced against solid bodies. There is, therefore, often the sound without any motion. Nor is it a simple motion, but one that is tremulous and vibratory. [...] I have found, by my inquiries, that the Alps and the Apennines are frequently shaken».

[In the original Latin text: «Praecedit vero comitaturque terribilis sonus, alias murmur mugitibus similis, aut clamori humano armorumve pulsantium fragori, pro qualitate materiae excipientis formaque vel cavernarum vel cuniculi per quem fit, exitus grassante in angusto eodem rauco in recurvis resultante in duris, fervente in umidis fluctuante in stagnantibus feruente contra solida. Itaque et sine motu saepe editur sonus; nec simplici modo quatitur unquam, sed tremit vibratque. [...] Exploratum est mihi alpes appenninumque tremuisse saepius»].

Fig. 102 - The sounds of earthquakes as described by Pliny the Elder in his *Naturalis historia* (from the first printed edition, Venice, 1469), p. 20-21

But wind is the cause, and when the pressure of winds lessens, the earthquake is over (Book II, Chapter LXXXIV)::

«The tremors cease when the vapour bursts out; but if they do not soon cease, they continue for forty days; generally, indeed, for a longer time: some have lasted even for one or two years».

[In the original Latin text: «Desinunt autem tremores cum ventus emergit; sin vero duraverint non ante XL dies sistuntur plerumque et tardius, utpote cum quidam annuo et biennii spacio duraverint»].

partem totus se motus impellit. Desinunt autem tremores cum uentus emergit: fin
uero durauerint non ante .xl. dies sistuntur plerunq; & tardius utpote cum quidam
annuo & biennii spacio durauerint. LXXXV

Fig. 103 - The cessation of earthquakes from Pliny the Elder's *Naturalis historia* (from the first printed edition, Venice, 1469), p. 21

Thus, throughout classical antiquity scholars have tried to explain the reason for the occurrence of earthquakes by adopting a prescientific model, based on winds circulating in the hidden hollows of the earth. Sometimes, winds exert a mighty pressure on their subterranean abodes, and their oscillating motion generates seismic effects on the surface; sometimes, they even succeed in escaping their underground prisons, so giving way to powerful storms which contribute to the overall destruction of the land above.

While the men of the Iron Age who lived amid the Apennines had confronted with the frightful seismic waves which recurrently struck their territory by possibly imagining a dream of demonic gods lurking beneath their mountains, the Greeks and Romans followed an utterly different path, impervious as it was in the lack of any solid scientific foundations, and yet based on fully natural, worldly considerations, with no need to introduce any god or demon: a path that will eventually lead the culture of the Western world to modern science as we know it today.

However, for the time being winds and tempest were the only available explanation to earthquakes. The advent of the Christian age will add substantially nothing to this conceptual framework, and the wind theory will remain undisputed until the Renaissance, as we noted in the *Zodiacus Vitae*, written by Marcellus Palingenius Stellatus in 1536.

And it is not by a mere chance that subterranean winds are also explicitly mentioned by the key authors of the sibilline legendary tradition, Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de la Sale:

In his *Guerrino the Wretch*, Andrea da Barberino sends his knight hero into the Purgatory of St. Patrick, immediately after his forbidden visit to the Apennine Sibyl. There, Guerrino is surrounded by angered demons, who

break in accompanied by a fiendish wind, which Andrea da Barberino openly associates to earthquakes (Chapter CLXVIII):

«The church began to tremble; and the air rumbled, and it seemed to him that the wind was blowing so strong that the earth quivered, as he had already heard and seen out of the winds, which erupt from the ground and are called earthquakes. But these were no earthquakes at all, they were fiendish demons...»

[In the original Italian text: «La giesia comenzò a tremare; e l'aere tonava, e parevali che si grande el vento traesse che la terra tremasse, come certe volte lui havea zia per venti sentito e veduto, che esseno de la terra, che sono chiamati terremoti. Ma questi non erano terremoti, anzi furono demonii infernali...»].

Fig. 104 - Winds and earthquakes as mentioned in Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino the Wretch* (from the edition printed in Venice in 1480)

And Antoine de la Sale, in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, lets his characters make an experience of the powerful subterranean winds which circulate beneath the earth, within the bowels of the Sibyl's Cave:

«So they went through that narrower hollow, going ahead for some three miles, as they reckoned. Then they found a crevice which split the cave: a wind issued forth from the crevice, so horrible and astounding that no one of them dared to go ahead of a single step, or even half of it; because, when they tried to get nearer, they felt that the wind was trying to carry them away».

[In the original French text: «Allerent par ceste plus basse cave, tousdiz en avalant, bien l'espace de trois milles a leur advis. Lors trouverent une vaine de terre traversant la cave, dont yssoit un vent si treshideux et merueilleux que ne fut celui qui osast aler pas ne demy plus avant; car, aussi tost qu'ilz approchoient, leur sembloit que le vent les emportast»].

Fig. 105 - Subterranean winds as portrayed by Antoine de la Sale in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folia 10r and 10v)

Winds and earthquakes. Winds which blow through the unseen hollows of the earth. An antique credence which is fully known to authors like Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de la Sale, who include mentions of it in their respective works.

From the Renaissance onwards, a renewed interest on the puzzling issue of the origin of earthquakes will bring scholars and philosophers to the production of additional conjectures, as for instance the theory proposed by Immanuel Kant on the combination of hot gases of sulphur and iron in subterranean caverns and pits.

It will eventually be in the nineteenth century that the physics of waves travelling through the earth will be discovered and studied. A century later

German scientist Alfred Wegener will set down his theory on continental drift and plate tectonics, the fundamental key to a scientific understanding of earthquake's nature and characteristics.

So, for more than seventeenth centuries, from Aristotle, Titus Lucretius Carus, Lucius Annaeus Seneca, Pliny the Elder and up to the late Middle Ages, earthquakes and winds and tempests will be part of a same, homogeneous vision of the mighty powers which conveyed destruction on earth.

And this identity of vision is fully retrievable in the literary tradition which concerns the legendary tales of the Sibillini Mountain Range, in the Italian Apennines.

A further indication that our conjecture, based on earthquakes and their terrifying effects, is bringing us on a promising course.

7. A new interpretation of the meaning of the mythical tale

In the present paper, we have presented a new hypothesis on the potential origin of the legendary tales which are found amid the Sibillini Mountain Range. We conjectured that, during the Iron Age, the local populations of Sabines and Picenes, recurrently struck by devastating earthquakes and ceaselessly exposed to the ominous tremors of the earth, may have established highland shrines at the Lake set on Mount Vettore and the Cave situated on the cliff of Mount Sibyl, which later legendary layers will transform into a Sibyl's Cave and a Lake of Pilate.

The terrifying cohabitation with the seismic shakings may have fostered the production of legendary credences that were possibly related to demonic beings who lived beneath the Sibillini Mountain Range: fiendish demons who presided over the earthquakes, and could be queried for mercy at two specific, emotionally-potent sites: the Lake and the Cave, both placed at eerie, uncanny settings. Two landmarks, two geographical features marking an entryway to a superhuman Otherworld.

Not a Sibyl, nor a Roman prefect. Instead, a personification of earthquakes: a most powerful and devastating might, typically smashing this Apennine land since time immemorial.

Earthquakes as an otherworldly power, deserving worship in search of protection and salvation.

We want to stress the fact that our conjecture, of which we have seen in the present paper a series of supporting considerations, is not foreign to the ancient cultures of Italy, both pre-Roman and Roman.

In our previous paper *Sibillini Mountain Range, a cave and lake to the Otherworld*, we already mentioned a most impressive passage taken from Book VI of the *Aeneid* by Publius Vergilius Maro, written in the first century B.C. When the Cumaean Sibyl, by art of necromancy, opens wide the gate of the frightful cave which is the entryway to Hades, by raising an appeal to Hecate, something absolutely appalling occurs.

It is earthquake:

«See now, at the dawn light of the rising sun,
the ground bellowed under their feet, the wooded hills began
to move, and, at the coming of the Goddess, dogs seemed to howl
in the shadows».

[In the original Latin text (lines 255-258):

«Ecce autem, primi sub lumina solis et ortus,
sub pedibus mugire solum, et iuga coepta moveri
silvarum, visaeque canes ululare per umbram,
adventante dea»].

The bellow of the ground at Cumae. The yell of the ravaged cliffs amid the the Sibillini Mountain Range. The mythical power of earthquakes travels far and wide across different populations and ages. But the terror experienced by human beings remains the same. And necromancy seems to be considered powerful enough to exert some kind of control over the chthonian powers, as shown by Vergil's text with poetical mastery.

Because the Romans, too, were in awe of earthquakes, despite all their efforts at finding prescientific explanations to this baleful phenomenon, as in the works written by Lucretius, Seneca and Pliny.

When the Roman troops swept the land of the Picenes in the year 268 B.C., and a fierce battle was being fought near Asculum, today's town of Ascoli, set on the eastern edge of the Sibillini Mountain Range, a visitors came uninvited amid the slaughter.

Again, it was earthquake.

And second-century Latin writer Lucius Annaeus Florus, in his *Epitomae de Tito Livio*, reports to us all the surprise and fear experienced, during the terrifying event, by the Roman commander, consul Publius Sempronius Sophus:

«The people of Picenum were therefore subdued and their capital Asculum was taken under the leadership of Sempronius, who, when an earthquake occurred in the midst of the battle, appeased the goddess Tellus by the promise of a temple».

[In the original Latin text: «Domiti ergo picentes et caput gentis asculum sempronio duce, qui tremente inter proelium campo tellurem deam promissa aede placavit»].

Fig. 106 - The excerpt on an earthquake near Asculum as drawn from Lucius Annaeus Florus' *Epitomae de Tito Livio* (ninth-century manuscript Pal. Lat. 894 preserved at the Universitätsbibliothek in Heidelberg), opening folium and folium 12v

While the appalling earthquake was visiting again the region of the Sibillini Mountain Range, certainly nobody stopped to consider pensively the remarkable winds that, according to the lesson of Aristotle, were seemingly pushing the ground from below: instead, in utter terror, they hastened to implore goddess Tellus, the Roman deity of the earth, for salvation and mercy. And, afterwards, they gratefully built a temple dedicated to the deity in downtown Rome.

When experienced personally, one senses with all one's body that earthquakes are a supernatural affair.

So no Apennine Sibyl has ever existed on the peaks of the Sibillini Mountain Range. Disguised by many extraneous legendary layers added to her semblance, her true features seem to faintly reemerge from the reference provided by Martino Delrio, a sixteenth-century Flemish author from which we already quoted in our previous article *Apennine Sibyl: the bright side and the dark side*. In his *Disquisitionum magicarum libri sex*, published in 1599, he places the Sibyl of Norcia within the ranks of subterranean demons, defined by Johannes Trithemius sixty years earlier.

But Trithemius, in his *Liber octo questionum ad Maximilianum Cesarem*, had written the following words (Quaestio Sexta):

«The fifth kind [of demons] is called subterranean: they are the ones who reside in caverns and caves and hollows placed under remote peaks. The power of such demons is utterly evil [...]. They are most willing to harm human beings. They can cause wind [...] to erupt from holes in the ground. And they can shake the foundations of buildings».

«Quintum genus subterraneum dicitur: quod in speluncis et cavernis montiumque remotis concavitatibus demorant. Et isti daemones affectione sunt pessimi. [...] In pernicie humani generis paratissimi. Hiatus efficiunt terrae, ventosque flamiuomos suscitant & fundamenta edificiorum concutiunt».]

The harm mankind. They open cracks in the earth. They raise fiery wind. They shake the foundations of buildings.

This is earthquake.

Fig. 107 - Earth tremors and winds associated to subterranean demons, from Johannes Trithemius' *Liber octo questionum ad Maximilianum Cesarem*

And the Apennine Sibyl, through a mediation which has lasted for millennia, from the Iron Age to Delrio and Trithemius, by this excerpt appears to have come back to her first nature and origin.

8. A conclusive remark and a farewell

More than two years ago, in the wake of one of the largest earthquakes ever occurred in the territory of the Sibillini Mountain Range, the author of the present paper began to suppose that the legendary narratives which have been living in the area for centuries may actually be connected to the peculiar, seismic nature of the territory.

With the elaboration of a novel on the legend of the Apennine Sibyl (*The eleventh Sibyl*, 2010), we started to collect a large amount of literary information and data on the historical research on the mythical tales of the Sibillini Mountain Range, including most interesting material on the recurrent earthquakes which had plagued the land in the previous centuries.

However, one patent fact could be noticed: no research information was available on the origin of the legendary tale of the Sibyl of the Apennines, while the narrative concerning the Lake of Pilate was manifestly connected to the known medieval legend of Pontius Pilate.

However, it seemed that the tale of the Apennine Sibyl had emerged from some sort of thick, impenetrable mist, and had manifested itself only in the fifteenth century, in the fascinating works written by Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de la Sale: *Guerrino the Wretch* and *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*.

Nobody had ever investigated what had happened in earlier times, and whether that Sibyl could be traced across the centuries of the Middle Ages. Only one thing seemed to be clear to scholars: the Apennine Sibyl was not included in the classical list of Sibyls, nor any reference to such a Sibyl had ever been retrieved in Roman or early-Christian literature.

But when, once again, the earthquakes hit the Sibillini Mountain Range in the year 2016, the mighty effects that were visible on the mountainsides and the sheer terror experienced by the local residents under the long sequence of ghastly shocks, suggested a new course of investigation.

A course that no scholar, in the past two centuries, had ever addressed.

The potential of the Sibillini Mountain Range as a generator of mythical tales connected to the nature and origin of the earthquakes was becoming apparent, especially when considered in a context of ancient pre-Roman populations inhabiting the area in a long-gone past.

However, this research topic could not be analysed and developed without addressing, in the first instance, the question of a potential medieval origin and evolution of the legends concerning the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate. This was a research step that was mandatorily required to bridge the considerable gap which was patently visible between the fifteenth-century literary witnesses available to us and any potential conjecture on a Roman or even pre-Roman original core of the myth inhabiting the Sibillini Mountain Range.

So in December 2017 we began to investigate the centuries before the fifteenth in further depth, in search of clues that might hint to a presence of our Apennine Sibyl across the medieval age. And the search was instantly rewarding.

We immediately stumbled upon a passage written by Ferdinando Neri, in his *The Italian traditions of the Sibyl (Le tradizioni italiane della Sibilla, 1913)*, in which the Italian scholar mentioned the «ever-slamming metal doors» that are present in the popular lore connected to visits to supernatural 'netherworlds': the same kind of otherwordly device which is depicted by Antoine de la Sale in his description of the Sibyl's Cave.

This opened the way to the first valuable finds of inherited literary themes and narrative topics in earlier chivalric works, such as *Huon of Bordeaux* and *Huon d'Auvergne*, and to preliminary observations concerning a possible link to other otherwordly narratives, like the tale on the Purgatory of St. Patrick and the Cumaen Hades.

Otherworld turned to be one of the main keywords in the legendary framework of the Sibillini Mountain Range: at the beginning of the year 2018, we could release two papers (*Antoine de La Sale and the magical bridge concealed beneath Mount Sibyl* and *The literary truth about the magical doors in 'The Paradise of Queen Sibyl'*) which proved the illustrious literary lineage of the otherwordly devices that Antoine de la Sale had reported as present within the Sibyl's Cave.

Following a successive series of articles, in January 2019 a further landmark paper was released (*Birth of a Sibyl: the medieval connection*), in which the literary character of the Apennine Sibyl was traced back to Morgan le Fay and her companion Sebile, the necromantic figures which fully belong to the medieval tradition of the Matter of Britain and the Arthurian cycle. In May 2019, another paper (*A legend for a Roman prefect: the Lakes of Pontius Pilate*) provided a full, comprehensive summary of the antique legend concerning the burial place of Pontius Pilate, a foreign tale that had possibly deposited itself amid the Sibillini Mountain Range during the fourteenth century, as specific details seemed to suggest.

As a result of the above research, the Sibyl of the Apennines and the Roman prefect could be positively considered as overlays, or additional legendary layers that had established themselves in central Italy during the High Middle Ages.

In September 2019, with the paper *Sibillini Mountain Range: the legend before the legends*, we explored and identified the common legendary traits which appear to lie beneath the mentioned overlays, with reference to both geographical features, the Lake and the Cave: necromancy, a demonic presence, tempests and devastation arising from the two sites.

Fig. 108 - Mount Sibyl at sunset

A fourth, major common aspect was fully detected and analysed in the subsequent paper (*Sibillini Mountain Range, a cave and lake to the Otherworld*): the possible role of both sites as legendary passageways to the Otherworld, an illustrious literary topic which, in the Western world, spans from the *Odyssey* to the *Aeneid*, and then to various early-Christian and medieval visions accounting for legendary visits to a realm of dead or a demonic Hell. Manifest narrative contaminations could be retrieved between the legends of the Sibillini Mountain Range and the otherworldly narratives concerning a classical entryway in Cumae, in southern Italy, and Lough Derg, the Irish entrance to the Purgatory of St. Patrick.

Throughout the whole investigation, it was patent the mighty attractive force exerted by the Lake and Cave set within the Sibillini Mountain Range on different, extraneous legendary material, coming from far-off lands and countries: Morgan and Sebile, Pontius Pilate, the Cumaean Sibyl and the Purgatory of St. Patrick.

With the present, conclusive paper, we investigated, at last, the inner, original core of the legends which inhabit the Sibillini Mountain Range, now finally deprived of all the additional legendary layers that have deposited themselves on this area, under the attraction of a most powerful mythical engine.

And the engine, the legendary dream set at the very base of all this is earthquakes.

Fig. 109 - Mount Vettore and the Lakes of Pilate

We conjectured that the pre-Roman inhabitants of the Sibillini Mountain Range feared the earthquakes the way as we fear them today. However, the tools available to them to understand the appalling phenomenon which

recurrently struck them with the utmost might were markedly different from ours. Our contemporary scientific knowledge helps us in the control of our fears. Instead, the ancient populations of Sabines and Picenes could only resort to myth, with the generation of legendary narratives.

Such narratives are wholly lost to us. Nonetheless, we may try to conjecture what sort of dreams they might have housed in their hearts before the appalling, harrowing potency of the earthquakes. A possible dream of demons, whose abode was beneath the mountain. The need for a contact, perhaps, with a view to ask for mercy and salvation. The eerie, sinister Lake and Cave as the most natural choices where to establish such hypothetical otherworldly contact. Physical points of access to a subterranean Otherworld, inhabited by supernatural, fiendish beings. Two 'hot spots' set amid precipitous mountains. Landmarks to legend.

This is, in our opinion, the wondrous thickness and amazing richness of the legendary framework which marks this most beautiful, most charming, absolutely outstanding land of central Italy: the Sibillini Mountain Range. A mythical abundance and wealth which is rarely achieved by other regions in the world.

As a final remark, we want to stress the fact that, amid the other landmarks to otherworldly passageways that antique legendary traditions have consigned to us, the Sibillini Mountain Range is certainly the less unfounded, the less fairy-like and for sure the most justified and understandable, mythical as it may be.

Because, if the Hades set in the caves of Cumae is merely linked to the volcanic nature of the place and the poisonous gases which filled those hollows, and the Purgatory of St. Patrick was just a sort of cellar for dupes, duly exhausted prior to their visit and then locked up within a small, oxygen-deprived space, the Sibillini Mountain Range was a place where terror actually ruled, and a demonic presence was tangibly clear and present throughout the years and the centuries: a true Otherworld of earthquakes.

It is in this very framework that the true significance of the ancient name of the Sibillini Mountain Range, as reported by Vergil in his *Aeneid*, may become totally apparent to our contemporary perception: «Tetricae

horrentis rupes», writes the great Latin author, «dreadful, sullen, gloomy cliff», a land of eerie mystery. And terror.

However, across the centuries people have only been aware of the renown of Lake Avernus in Cumae and Lough Dergh in Ireland. It is now time to bestow on the Sibillini Mountain Range the fame and merit it deserves, out of the astounding quality and underlying substance of its legend.

Of course, the conjectural scenario presented in this paper will need further confirmations.

We do not know whether future potential excavations at the Lake and Cave might possibly ascertain the presence of any remnants of the hypothetical highland shrines we envisaged, in the forms of votive offerings or even bone remains deposited at the two sites across the centuries of the Iron Age. Sure enough, if any such remnant still exists, it is buried beneath many feet of debris and rubble at the bottom of the Lake, and thick layers of collapsed rocks within the Cave, or even in unreachable pits down in the same Cave. However, we fully subscribe to the reasearch line already envisaged by Pio Rajna, the Italian philologist, in 1912:

«Our considerations suggest that the idea that the Sibyl's cave may have been a site of worship well before Rome established its rule over that region is not a daring assumption [...] If our conjecture is correct, deeper excavations may possibly lead to the unearthing of votive offerings».

[In the original Italian text: «Si dica dopo tutto ciò se sia congettura avventata il pensiero che la caverna della Sibilla sia stata un luogo di culto ben prima che Roma distendesse su quella regione il suo dominio [...] Se la congettura coglie nel segno, scavi non superficiali avrebbero presumibilmente da condurre alla scoperta di oggetti votivi»].

But the major and most significant portion of the future researches on the Sibillini Mountain Range will rest, in our opinion, upon further historical and archeological investigations on the culture and beliefs of the Sabines and Picenes, in connection with the fact that additional, deeper enquiries at many sites across and around the Sibillini Mountain Range are still needed.

simbolo di santità, ben si poteva vedere nella fascia di roccia. Si dica dopo tutto ciò se sia congettura avventata il pensiero che la caverna della Sibilla sia stata un luogo di culto ben prima che Roma distendesse su quella regione il suo dominio, e che dell'interminabile

la leggenda di Tannhäuser. Se la congettura coglie nel segno, scavi non superficiali avrebbero presumibilmente da condurre alla scoperta di oggetti votivi. Basterebbe forse nondimeno che mettessero a nudo

Fig. 110 - The words written by Pio Rajna in his article *Nei paraggi della Sibilla di Norcia*, from *Studi dedicati a Francesco Torraca nel XXXVI anniversario della sua laurea* (Napoli, 1912), p. 252-253

So our long travel through the fascinating legends that are found in the very heart of Italy, immersed in the gorgeous scenery of the Sibillini Mountain Range, is nearing its end.

As in a sort of 'reverse engineering' process, we have unravelled the thorny tangle of different legends which makes up the complex legendary system that lives on the cliffs of central Apennine, in Italy. To perform this challenging, stimulating task we have retraced backwards the legendary, intertwined threads that centuries have been weaving over these amazing mountains.

We are proud to have been part of a long, illustrious chain of scholars who, across one hundred fifty years, have confronted with the enigmatic questions posed by the legendary tales of the Apennine Sibyl and the Lake of Pilate, in search of a truth that was so charming and at the same time so elusive. We had the chance to share the same dreams that other great academics, philologists and men of letters have housed in their hearts: from Alfred von Reumont to Arturo Graf, from Gaston Paris to Pio Rajna, from Lucy Ann Paton to Ferdinando Neri, and then Roger S. Loomis, Fernand Desonay, Domenico Falzetti, and Luigi Paolucci, a brilliant mind who was so keen as to pinpoint, neatly and confidently, the right course that research had to adopt to solve this legendary riddle.

They all were fascinated by the spell which hovers around the lofty peaks of the Sibillini Mountain Range. Many of them had a lifelong dream in their soul: they wanted to find a solution to the enigma. And yet, they did not possess the right key, the very peculiar one that unlocked the door to the inner core of the mystery. A deeper understanding, which can only be

reached by those who know, even by direct experience, what an earthquake is.

And we are sure that, if we had now the chance to speak to them, their eyes would shine with riveted amazement, while listening to a conjecture which provides comprehensive answers to many of the questions they happened to pose to themselves as to the legends of the Sibillini Mountains Range. Because we have provided a possible, motivated answer to the most fundamental question of all, the question that a philologist, Paolo Toschi, and his brilliant pupil, Luigi Paolucci, stated many decades ago:

«Why were these very places, and not different ones, inhabited by the Sibyl, and why did necromancers use to come here to consecrate their spellbooks?».

[In the original Italian text: «Ma perché proprio in questi determinati luoghi e non in altri abitava la Sibilla, e i maghi vengono a consacrare il libro del Comando?»].

This is the very same question we posed to ourselves during our search, when we stated it in our previous papers *Birth of a Sibyl: the medieval connection* and *A legend for a Roman prefect: the Lakes of Pontius Pilate*: what sort of magnetic pull did attract so many magical, estraneous legendary narratives on the peaks of Mount Vettore and Mount Sibyl? For what kind of fated chance did an Apennine Sibyl and a Roman prefect, accompanied by eerie tales about devastating storms, come to rest, like a ball spinning on a roulette wheel, right into the position marked by these remote Italian mountains?

At that time, we had already begun to repute that so mighty a pull might arise from some odd condensation of any peculiar nature of this region, the Sibillini Mountain Range; an effect generated by some unknown local factor, a result of the physical peculiarities of this wondrous territory: peculiarities which rendered it able to generate a powerful mythical attraction for highly-emotional legendary narratives.

And the specific peculiarity of this land, the Sibillini Mountain Range, is earthquakes.

Earthquakes: «the most horrible event that the world we inhabit offers to our sight», as Leopoldo Mannocchi wrote in 1859, «a thoroughly frightful scourge, which many times has struck and ruined this town [Norcia]».

[In the original Italian text: «il più terribile dei fenomeni che sottoponga a' nostri sguardi il pianeta da noi abitato, il paurosissimo flagello del tremuoto, che assai volte avea costernata e concussa questa città»].

Il più terribile dei fenomeni che sottoponga a' nostri sguardi il pianeta da noi abitato, il paurosissimo flagello del tremuoto, che assai volte avea costernata e concussa questa città (1) sembrava essersi

Fig. 111 - A description of earthquakes written by Abbot Leopoldo Mannocchi in his *Relazione del terremoto che desolò Norcia...* (Roma, 1860), p. 7 and 8

An horrifying event, which is so heinous as to give origin to such hair-raising descriptions as we find in the chronicles concerning the devastating earthquake that occurred in the year 1703:

«At 1:45 in the night of the said day, so fierce and terrifying an Earthquake came, followed by many others, as frightful as the first tremblor, across the whole duration of that grievous night, and accompanied by thunderbolts, lightnings, sulphurous smells, and by so many ceaseless shakes of the ground, that in addition to the whole destruction of Norcia, it seemed that it was determined to swallow everything in the land above, now swelling and then subsiding together with all the buildings, and then swaying from one side to the other; this havoc was multiplied by the roaring noise of the collapsing walls, blood-curdling wails, direful outcries, voices coming from beneath the ruins».

[In the original Italian text: «Ad un'ora, e quasi tre quarti di notte del detto giorno venne un così fiero e terribile Terremoto, seguito da molti altri di non minore spavento in tutto lo spazio di quella funestissima notte, ed accompagnato da' tuoni, da' lampi, da fetori bituminosi, e da così continovi tremori della terra, che oltre l'intero eccidio di Norcia, sembrava che assorbir volesse quanto le stava di sopra, or'alzandosi, or'abbassandosi

quasi tutte le fabbriche, e quando agitavansi da una banda, e quando dall'altra; al che si aggiugnevano lo strepitoso fragore delle mura, che rovesciavano, strida spaventose, clamori terribili, e voci sotterranee»].

salvarono da tante, e si spaventevoli rovine; ad un' ora, e quasi tre quarti di notte del detto giorno venne un così fiero e terribile 'Terremoto, seguito da molti altri di non minore spavento in tutto lo spazio di quella funestissima notte, ed accompagnato da' tuoni, da' lampi, da' piogge, da' oscurità tenebrose, da' puzze solfuree, da' fetori bituminosi, e da così continovi tremori della terra, che oltre l'intero eccidio di Norcia, sembrava che assorbir volesse quanto le stava di sopra, or'alzandosi, or'abbassandosi quasi tutte le fabbriche, e quando agitavansi da una banda, e quando dall'altra; al che si aggiugnevano lo strepitoso fragore delle mura, che rovesciavano, strida spaventose, clamori terribili, e voci sotterranee.

Fig. 112 - The dreadful effects of the earthquake occurred in central Italy in 1703 from *Cronologia della provincia serafica riformata dell'Umbria, o d'Assisi divisa in tre libri raccolta, ordinata, e data in luce dal padre Antonio d'Orvieto* (Perugia, 1717), p. 271

Life and death, bodily existence and supernatural powers, mortality and fiendish divinity: the basic hopes and terrors which are housed in the hearts of men and women found a most fit abode at this small portion of Italy and Europe.

So our work is completed. It is now up to scholars and researchers to continue along the path we have traced, or to reject it.

We only want to add one more, and final, consideration.

Maybe the model we set down, involving earthquakes and legendary demons presiding over them, may sound as preposterous, and even somewhat foolhardy, if not utterly foolish.

To this sort of criticism, we do not intend to reply by putting forward, again, the many considerations we already presented in this research paper.

We just intend to provide a different, far more effective answer.

Because, in the year 2016, as we already know, many mighty earthquakes struck the Sibillini Mountain Range.

And on November, 28th 2019, three years later, the Italian news agency ANSA released a number of interviews recorded by a local correspondent, Gianluigi Basilietti, at Castelluccio di Norcia, the small hamlet set in the middle of the region, a settlement that was entirely demolished by the terrific seismic waves.

Fig. 113 - Sibillini Mountain Range: Castelluccio di Norcia ravaged by the fury of the earthquake in 2016

A man was interviewed. An elderly man, who was born in Castelluccio and, though now living in Rome, had resided for most of his life before the precipitous versants of Mount Vettore. He was a man of our present times, so what he said is only a faint shadow of the feelings that the ancient inhabitants of the Sibillini Mountain Range may have housed in their hearts in a far-away antiquity, when the earthquake hit their dwellings and land with its utmost potency.

And yet, his words, though uttered by contemporary lips, were thoroughly impressive:

«... Suddenly, a Fiend arrives from underneath», he said, «and tears down everything» (in the original Italian words: «... poi arriva il Diavolo sotto, e sfascia tutto»).

A Fiend arrives, from beneath. And devastates the whole land.

The Iron Age, in the Sibillini Mountain Range, suddenly seems to reach out to us through an unfathomable span of time: on the eerie, divine, terrifying waves of earthquakes.

Michele Sanvico

END OF PART 2

**Please refer to Part 1
for the first section of this research paper**